
Stoquastic Hamiltonians and the Monte Carlo Sign Problem

Marios Ioannou

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Marios Ioannou

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Marios Ioannou

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Erstgutachter: Prof. Barbara Terhal

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Chapter 0

Introduction

Since their introduction 40 years ago, Monte Carlo methods have proven successful in providing numerical results to problems which cannot be solved by hand. Such problems can range from evaluating thermodynamic properties of complex physical systems, to doing Bayesian inferencing [34],[28]. In the study of physical models, the method was initially limited to the analysis of classical Hamiltonians. With the introduction of the *quantum to classical* mapping by Suzuki, Miyashita and Kudora [44], which gave rise to the *world-line* Monte Carlo method, it became possible to apply the method to quantum many-body problems. Since then, a high degree of sophistication has been reached, with many variations of the quantum Monte Carlo method existing, more or less adapted to certain types of problems [48]. Despite this immense development, one of the main impediments of the method, known as the sign problem remains to this date. The sign problem has its roots in the fact that the quantum to classical mapping gives rise to a quasi-probability distribution one needs to sample from using the Monte Carlo method [17]. Different approaches to overcome the sign problem have been proposed, exploiting symmetries of the problem to show that under certain circumstances the quasi-probability distribution is in fact an ordinary distribution [19], [18], [42]. In [9] so-called stoquastic Hamiltonians were introduced. This class of Hamiltonians, by definition, does not suffer from the sign problem. The notion of stoquasticity is basis dependent and as such it is obvious to ask for which classes of Hamiltonians it is possible to find an appropriate basis in which to represent the Hamiltonians, so as to avoid the sign problem. This was first studied in [27] where an efficient algorithm, finding an appropriate representation for a large class of Hamiltonians was introduced. In an independent work [33] it was shown that deciding whether a 6-local Hamiltonian can be transformed into a stoquastic form, using local orthogonal rotations, is a **NP**-complete problem. In [26] we closed the gap between these two results, showing that the initial algorithm can be generalised to strictly two-local Hamiltonians. We furthermore, showed that deciding existence of local unitary rotations, turning a two-local Hamiltonian with one-local terms, into a stoquastic form, is still a **NP**-complete problem. The arguments utilised for these results are based on the framework of computational complexity theory. Using Complexity theory, one can study the required effort, with respect to some chosen resource (e.g time) to solve a given problem [4]. Despite being primarily a tool used in

theoretical computer science, complexity theoretic arguments have been applied to quantify the difficulty of physically relevant problems, e.g the ground energy problem for Ising Hamiltonians [6] and general quantum Hamiltonians [25]. In a series of papers [9], [10], [8], [7] and more recently [2] the complexity of the ground energy problem for stoquastic Hamiltonians has been studied extensively. It was shown that stoquastic Hamiltonians are special in the sense that they lie between classical and generic quantum Hamiltonians when it comes to the complexity of evaluating their ground energy.

In order to achieve as linear a structure as possible, we will start in the first chapter with an introduction to the Markov chain Monte Carlo method and the sign problem therein. After presenting the fundamental principles of Monte Carlo simulations, we will discuss the main pathologies of the Monte Carlo method, namely the sign problem and convergence issues. In the second chapter we will introduce the notion of stoquasticity; differentiating between global and local stoquasticity, providing the first in-depth analysis of the distinction between the two notions. The third chapter will start by introducing some of the fundamental concepts of complexity theory. Here we will present those classes most relevant to the remainder of the thesis and to the study of stoquastic Hamiltonians in general. We will then discuss a formal version of the ground energy problem, known as the Local Hamiltonian problem, in the general setting as well as in light of stoquastic Hamiltonians and general sign problem free Hamiltonians, see Proposition 9. In the fourth and final chapter we will go over the problem of deciding whether a Hamiltonian is stoquastic, either in a fixed basis or under basis transformations. In an original proof, see Theorem 6, we will show, that even in a fixed basis, deciding stoquasticity is a **coNP**-complete problem. Allowing local unitary transformations we will show in Theorem 7, that the problem of deciding whether a Hamiltonian is effectively stoquastic, is in general **NP**-complete (as we presented in [26]). Finally, we will present a novel approach towards curing the sign problem for 1-D, two-local Hamiltonians using Clifford transformations, showing in Propositions 14 and 15 that a large class of 1-D Hamiltonians are effectively stoquastic.

Chapter 1

Monte Carlo methods

Numerical simulations based on Monte Carlo methods are among the oldest and most successful techniques for analysing problems for which an analytical approach is not available [34]. They have seen application in solid state physics, statistical physics, soft condensed matter [28] as well as other areas of science such as artificial intelligence [34]. We will introduce the Monte Carlo method as a means to sample from arbitrary probability distributions. Here we will give a comprehensive overview of the fundamental principles of Monte Carlo simulations, focusing on the application to quantum/classical statistical physics problems. One of the great breakthroughs of statistical physics was the realisation that the microstates of a system are distributed according to the Gibbs/Boltzmann probability distribution which relates the likelihood of a particular state occurring, to its energy [29]. If one was given some black box producing such states for a given system, distributed according to the Gibbs distribution, it would be possible to obtain an estimate for the expectation value of some quantity g , e.g free energy, using the sample average [31].

1.1 Classical Monte Carlo

To make the above discussion mathematically precise, let there be a function $g(\mathbf{x})$ with random variable \mathbf{x} , distributed according to some probability distribution $P(\mathbf{x})$. The expectation value of g is given by

$$\mathbb{E}_g = \sum_{\mathbf{x}} g(\mathbf{x})P(\mathbf{x}).$$

Being able to generate random samples of \mathbf{x} according to the distribution $P(\mathbf{x})$, we can approximate the expectation value by the sample mean

$$\mathbb{E}_g \approx \bar{g} := \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n g(\mathbf{x}_i).$$

How close the sample mean is to the expectation value of g , can be expressed by means of the Chebyshev inequality [46]:

$$\mathbb{P}(|\bar{g} - \mathbb{E}(\bar{g})| \geq \epsilon) \leq \frac{\text{Var}(\bar{g})}{\epsilon^2}.$$

If the samples drawn, \mathbf{x}_i , are independent and identically distributed, by linearity of expectation $\mathbb{E}(\bar{g}) = \mathbb{E}_g$. Similarly $\text{Var}(\bar{g}) = \frac{\text{Var}(g)}{n}$. So the probability of the sample mean being ϵ far from the expectation value is bounded by $\text{Var}(g)/\epsilon^2 n$. Therefore the number of required samples, n , to achieve a certain degree of confidence in the approximation, will depend on the variance of the variable g . As long as $\text{Var}(g)$ is bounded, in the limit of $n \rightarrow \infty$, one obtains the law of large numbers, $\bar{g} \rightarrow \mathbb{E}_g$ [31], since $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{P}(|\bar{g} - \mathbb{E}_g| \geq \epsilon) = 0$. The bottleneck of this approach is our ability to sample $g(\mathbf{x}_i)$ distributed according to $P(\mathbf{x})$, especially in high dimensional spaces where the probability density can be concentrated in very confined regions [34]. There are several methods for sampling probability distributions, such as importance or rejection sampling; however, most of them ultimately fail in the general setting [31]. Here we will focus on one of the most successful approaches, in particular for physically relevant problems, known as Markov-chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) sampling.

1.1.1 Markov chains

Markov chains describe memoryless, stochastic processes i.e processes for which the state of the system evolves according to some probability distribution, which is not conditioned on its state at earlier times [21],[41].

$$\mathbb{P}(\sigma^t = \mathbf{x}^t | \sigma^1 = \mathbf{x}^1, \dots, \sigma^{t-1} = \mathbf{x}^{t-1}) = \mathbb{P}(\sigma^t = \mathbf{x}^t | \sigma^{t-1} = \mathbf{x}^{t-1}),$$

where $\forall t, \mathbf{x}^t \in \Omega$, the system-specific state space. We define the transition probability from state \mathbf{y} at time t to state \mathbf{x} in the next time step as

$$T(\mathbf{y}, \mathbf{x}) := \mathbb{P}(\sigma^{t+1} = \mathbf{x} | \sigma^t = \mathbf{y})$$

and denote the initial probability distribution by $\mathbb{P}(\sigma^1 = \mathbf{x})$. Given the transition probability and the starting distribution, we have fully specified the Markov chain. The probability of being in state \mathbf{x} at time $t + 1$ is given by

$$\mathbb{P}(\sigma^{t+1} = \mathbf{x}) = \sum_{\mathbf{y}} \mathbb{P}(\sigma^t = \mathbf{y}) T(\mathbf{y}, \mathbf{x}).$$

In order to sample from some predefined distribution e.g Gibbsian, we will make use of the fact that Markov chains, on finite state spaces, have stationary distributions for which the probability of finding the process in state \mathbf{x} is given by

$$\pi(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{\mathbf{y}} \pi(\mathbf{y}) T(\mathbf{y}, \mathbf{x}). \quad (1.1)$$

As the name suggests and, indeed can be seen from the condition, once the Markov chain reaches a stationary distribution, it will stay in that distribution for all future times. Therefore, by constructing a Markov chain with $\pi(\mathbf{x}) = P(\mathbf{x})$ and transition probabilities satisfying Equation 1.1, we can sample from $P(\mathbf{x})$ once the Markov chain has reached its stationary distribution. If we can do this for some distribution of interest, we can obtain the expectation value of observables, distributed according to $P(\mathbf{x})$, by sampling from $\pi(\mathbf{x})$ [41],[34]. In general, the stationary distribution need not be unique. Under certain conditions we can, however, guarantee uniqueness of the stationary distribution.

Definition 1. A state \mathbf{x} is said to be accessible from state \mathbf{y} if the probability of reaching \mathbf{x} in a finite number of steps is non-zero [41].

$$\mathbb{P}(\sigma^t = \mathbf{x} \mid \sigma^1 = \mathbf{y}) > 0.$$

If \mathbf{y} is also accessible from \mathbf{x} we say that the two states communicate.

Definition 2. The chain $X = \{\mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_n\}$ is irreducible if all states communicate with each other [21].

In other words a chain is irreducible if every state can be reached from every other state.

Definition 3. A state \mathbf{x} is recurrent if, after a finite number of steps, the chain returns to \mathbf{x} with certainty [41].

$$\mathbb{P}(t_j < \infty \mid \sigma^1 = \mathbf{x}) = 1,$$

where $t_j = \min[t > 1 : \sigma^t = \mathbf{x}]$ is the first time the chain is in state \mathbf{x} .

Definition 4. A state \mathbf{x} is aperiodic if [41]

$$\forall t \quad \mathbb{P}(\sigma^t = \mathbf{x} \mid \sigma^1 = \mathbf{x}) > 0.$$

If an aperiodic state \mathbf{x} communicates with \mathbf{y} , it follows that the later is also aperiodic. It can be shown that a Markov chain possesses a unique stationary distribution if it is irreducible and aperiodic [21]. Furthermore it can be shown that, independently of the initial state, the distribution of the Markov chain tends asymptotically to this unique stationary distribution

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{P}(\sigma^t = \mathbf{x} \mid \sigma^1 = \mathbf{y}) = \pi(\mathbf{x}),$$

if all states are recurrent and aperiodic. This property is commonly referred to as ergodicity [41].

Proposition 1. For a recurrent, aperiodic Markov chain $X = (\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2, \dots, \mathbf{x}_n)$ with invariant distribution $\pi(\mathbf{x})$ the following law of large numbers holds for any integrable function $g : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{t} \sum_{i=1}^t g(\mathbf{x}_i) \longrightarrow \sum_{\mathbf{x}} g(\mathbf{x}) \pi(\mathbf{x})$$

. [41]

Clearly, this is the condition we need to satisfy in order to be able to obtain the expectation value of some function $g(\mathbf{x})$ by means of evaluating the sample mean. In practice, one tries to obtain a good approximation of the expectation value by allowing the chain to reach the equilibrium distribution during the "burn in" phase and finally collect samples from which the sample average and variance are calculated [28].

The objective of Markov chain Monte Carlo reduces to constructing chains in such a way that their stationary distribution is the one we want to sample from, while ensuring that they are aperiodic and irreducible. For a given Markov chain, checking whether Equation 1.1 holds, is often impractical [31]. In practice it is much easier to check whether the stronger but *sufficient* "detailed balance" condition is satisfied

$$\pi(\mathbf{x})T(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \pi(\mathbf{y})T(\mathbf{y}, \mathbf{x}) \quad (1.2)$$

Proposition 2. *If the detailed balance condition is satisfied for a given transition probability and some distribution $\pi(\mathbf{x})$, the chain is said to be time reversible ($\mathbb{P}(\sigma^t = \mathbf{x} | \sigma^{t+1} = \mathbf{y}) = \mathbb{P}(\sigma^t = \mathbf{x} | \sigma^{t-1} = \mathbf{y})$) with respect to $\pi(\mathbf{x})$ and the invariant distribution of the chain is given by $\pi(\mathbf{x})$ [21].*

Proof. By summing over all \mathbf{y} and using the fact that $\sum_{\mathbf{y}} T(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = 1$, we get

$$\sum_{\mathbf{y}} \pi(\mathbf{x})T(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \sum_{\mathbf{y}} \pi(\mathbf{y})T(\mathbf{y}, \mathbf{x}) \implies \pi(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{\mathbf{y}} \pi(\mathbf{y})T(\mathbf{y}, \mathbf{x}),$$

recovering Equation 1.1.

To show that the process is time reversible

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{P}(\sigma^t = \mathbf{x} | \sigma^{t+1} = \mathbf{y}) &= \frac{\mathbb{P}(\sigma^t = \mathbf{x} \cap \sigma^{t+1} = \mathbf{y})}{\mathbb{P}(\sigma^{t+1} = \mathbf{y})} = \frac{\pi(\mathbf{x})T(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y})}{\pi(\mathbf{y})} \\ &= \frac{\pi(\mathbf{y})T(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y})}{\pi(\mathbf{y})} = \mathbb{P}(\sigma^t = \mathbf{y} | \sigma^{t+1} = \mathbf{x}) = \mathbb{P}(\sigma^t = \mathbf{x} | \sigma^{t-1} = \mathbf{y}) \end{aligned}$$

□

As discussed, a Markov chain is fully defined by the starting probability distribution and transition probabilities $T(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y})$. Possible methods for setting up the Markov chain will therefore vary in the way these are defined. There are various methods which allow us to construct a Markov Chain with the desired invariant distribution. Most used are so called Gibbs samplers, the Metropolis algorithm (which we will discuss in detail) and variations thereof [31].

1.1.2 Metropolis algorithm

In the following section we will study one particular way of choosing the transition probabilities, known as the Metropolis algorithm [21].

Metropolis algorithm: Define the starting state \mathbf{x}^1

1. Propose a move to a new state \mathbf{x} according to a *proposal* distribution $Q(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{x}^{t-1})$, properly normalised such that $\sum_{\mathbf{x}} Q(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{x}^{t-1}) = 1$.

2. Compute

$$\alpha(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{x}^{t-1}) = \min \left[1, \frac{f(\mathbf{x})Q(\mathbf{x}^{t-1}|\mathbf{x})}{f(\mathbf{x}^{t-1})Q(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{x}^{t-1})} \right],$$

where $f(\mathbf{x}) = CP(\mathbf{x})$ is the, possibly unnormalised, probability distribution we want to sample from.

3. Accept the move and set $\mathbf{x}^t = \mathbf{x}$ with probability $\alpha(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{x}^{t-1})$. Otherwise reject and set $\mathbf{x}^t = \mathbf{x}^{t-1}$.

Note that the transition probability can be computed without knowledge of the normaliser of the distribution. We will now show that the transition probabilities coming from the Metropolis algorithm satisfy the detailed balance condition and furthermore, give a condition for the chain to be ergodic.

Lemma 0.1. *The transition probability for the Metropolis algorithm is given by*

$$T(\mathbf{x}^{t-1}, \mathbf{x}^t) = \alpha(\mathbf{x}^t|\mathbf{x}^{t-1})Q(\mathbf{x}^t|\mathbf{x}^{t-1}) + (1 - \alpha(\mathbf{x}^{t-1}))\delta(\mathbf{x}^{t-1}, \mathbf{x}^t).$$

[34]

Proof. We have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{P}(\mathbf{x}^t \in \Omega|\mathbf{x}^{t-1}) &= \mathbb{P}(\mathbf{x}^t \in \Omega, \text{accept move}|\mathbf{x}^{t-1}) \\ &\quad + \mathbb{P}(\mathbf{x}^t \in \Omega, \text{reject move}|\mathbf{x}^{t-1}) \\ &= \sum_{\mathbf{x}^t \in \Omega} \alpha(\mathbf{x}^t|\mathbf{x}^{t-1})Q(\mathbf{x}^t|\mathbf{x}^{t-1}) + (1 - \alpha(\mathbf{x}^{t-1}))\delta(\mathbf{x}^{t-1}, \mathbf{x}^t) \end{aligned}$$

□

Proposition 3. *The transition probabilities for the Metropolis algorithm satisfy the detailed balance condition, Equation 1.2, with invariant distribution $f(\mathbf{x})$ [21]*

$$T(\mathbf{x}^{t-1}, \mathbf{x}^t)f(\mathbf{x}^{t-1}) = T(\mathbf{x}^t, \mathbf{x}^{t-1})f(\mathbf{x}^t)$$

Proof. Using the definition of $\alpha(\mathbf{x}^t|\mathbf{x}^{t-1})$ we get that

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha(\mathbf{x}^t|\mathbf{x}^{t-1})Q(\mathbf{x}^t|\mathbf{x}^{t-1})f(\mathbf{x}^{t-1}) &= \min [f(\mathbf{x}^{t-1})Q(\mathbf{x}^t|\mathbf{x}^{t-1}), f(\mathbf{x}^t)Q(\mathbf{x}^{t-1}|\mathbf{x}^t)] \\ &= \alpha(\mathbf{x}^{t-1}|\mathbf{x}^t)Q(\mathbf{x}^{t-1}|\mathbf{x}^t)f(\mathbf{x}^t) \end{aligned}$$

Combining this with Lemma 0.1 we find that

$$T(\mathbf{x}^{t-1}, \mathbf{x}^t)f(\mathbf{x}^{t-1}) = T(\mathbf{x}^t, \mathbf{x}^{t-1})f(\mathbf{x}^t)$$

□

Proposition 4. *The Markov chain generated by the Metropolis algorithm is recurrent if it is irreducible [45].*

Combining this with Proposition 1, we conclude that the Markov chain generated by the Metropolis algorithm is ergodic in the sense that the sample average of any integrable function converges to the expectation value [21]. Whether the Markov chain set up through the Metropolis algorithm is irreducible or not, will depend on the chosen proposal distribution. Clearly, a sufficient condition for this to be the case is

$$Q(\mathbf{x}^t|\mathbf{x}^{t-1}) \neq 0 \quad \forall \mathbf{x}^t, \mathbf{x}^{t-1},$$

since it implies that every state can be reached by every state in a single step.

For concreteness let's consider the task of calculating expectation values of thermodynamic quantities of some physical system [31]. Let H be a classical Hamiltonian, for example an Ising model Hamiltonian. Given some interaction graph $G = (V, E)$

$$H = \sum_{(i,j) \in E} J_{ij} Z_i Z_j + \sum_{i \in V} h_i Z_i,$$

where J_{ij} are coupling strengths and h_i is the strength of the local fields. As H is diagonal in the computational basis, its energy $E(S_1, \dots, S_n)$ is determined by the configuration of $S_i \in \{+1, -1\} \forall i$. Recall that the configurations of a system are distributed according to the Gibbs probability distribution [29]:

$$P(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{e^{-\beta E(S_1, \dots, S_n)}}{Z},$$

where $Z = \sum_{\{S\}} e^{-\beta E(S_1, \dots, S_n)}$ is the partition function. The expectation value of O is thus given by:

$$\mathbb{E}_O = \sum_{(S_1, \dots, S_n)} O(S_1, \dots, S_n) \frac{e^{-\beta E(S_1, \dots, S_n)}}{Z}.$$

For simplicity, let's consider a proposal distribution which flips a single spin $S_i \rightarrow -S_i$ at random. Clearly, this proposal distribution is time symmetric in the sense that $Q(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{x}^{t-1}) = Q(\mathbf{x}^{t-1}|\mathbf{x})$ leading to

$$\alpha(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{x}^{t-1}) = \min \left[1, \frac{f(\mathbf{x})}{f(\mathbf{x}^{t-1})} \right] = \min \left[1, e^{-\beta(E(S_1, \dots, S_i, \dots, S_n) - E(S_1, \dots, -S_i, \dots, S_n))} \right].$$

We see therefore, that the algorithm will always accept a move when the proposed configuration has lower energy, while it will accept moves which increase the energy of the configuration with probability $e^{-\beta(E(S_1, \dots, S_i, \dots, S_n) - E(S_1, \dots, -S_i, \dots, S_n))}$. As we have noted before, one does not need to know the normaliser, i.e the partition function in order to evaluate \mathbb{E}_O . If one wants to get an estimate for the partition function a little more work is required and we will see how to deal with this when we discuss the Monte Carlo method applied to quantum Hamiltonians.

When using the Metropolis algorithm we could, in principle, consider optimising the starting configuration if there exists physical intuition regarding a good ansatz. However, when choosing the proposal distribution $Q(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{x}^{t-1})$ it is essential to make an appropriate choice, ensuring that the chain is irreducible. The choice of proposal distribution influences the rate of convergence to the stationary distribution and ergodicity of the Markov chain. The updating scheme considered in the previous example, flipping a single spin at every time step, is the simplest we could consider. In section 4.2 we will see that such local updates might lead to a non-ergodic Markov chain and therefore we often need to go one step further. This can be done using "cluster updates" [34], flipping multiple spins at a time. If performed correctly, these have the advantage of avoiding non-ergodicity due to topological obstructions which might be present [48]. The downside of using such an updating scheme is that it can lead to many more steps being rejected as well as making rate of convergence analysis more difficult [31].

Given an ergodic Markov chain, such as the one constructed through the application of the Metropolis algorithm, it is guaranteed that in the limit $t \rightarrow \infty$ the Markov chain will have equilibrated to the stationary distribution, independently from the starting state \mathbf{x}^1 . However, there is a priori no statement about the rate at which the chain approaches the stationary distribution [31], [32]. It should be noted that under some reasonable assumptions we don't expect the Markov-chain constructed to *always* converge to the stationary distribution in polynomial time. This can be understood by the fact that there are "hard" optimisation problems, such as the ground energy problem for the Ising Hamiltonian (see section 3.3) which are not believed to be efficiently solvable. It is in fact rather difficult to find rigorous bounds on the equilibration time and in most cases such bounds do not exist [32]. We will discuss one particular convergence result in the context of quantum Hamiltonians in chapter four.

1.2 Quantum Monte Carlo

Extending our approach, we want to see how Monte Carlo techniques can be adapted to simulate quantum mechanical systems. Here we will concentrate on the so-called "world-line" Monte Carlo method which closely resembles our previous discussion, but it should be noted that other methods exist [28].

In contrast to the situation in classical statistical physics, the Hamiltonian for quantum mechanical systems is not diagonal in the computational basis. This means that the expectation value of some observable \hat{O} is expressed as [48]:

$$\langle \hat{O} \rangle = \frac{\text{Tr}(\hat{O} \exp(-\beta H))}{\text{Tr}(\exp(-\beta H))} = \frac{\sum_x \langle x | \hat{O} \exp(-\beta H) | x \rangle}{\sum_x \langle x | \exp(-\beta H) | x \rangle},$$

where for some n qubit Hamiltonian, H has dimension $2^n \times 2^n$. The time complexity for calculating $\sum_x \langle x | \exp(-\beta H) | x \rangle$ scales exponentially in the system size as it involves diagonalising exponentially large matrices, making this method impractical [40]. One way forward would be to manipulate the expression in such a way as to allow evaluation of

$\langle x | \exp(-\beta H) | x \rangle$ by determining matrix elements $\langle x | H | y \rangle$. As long as H is local, these matrix elements can be determined efficiently, as they only involve $poly(n)$ terms. This can be achieved by writing [11]:

$$e^{-\beta H} = [e^{-\beta H/N}]^N,$$

often referred to as *Trotterization* and subsequently expanding to first order in β/N [17]

$$e^{-\beta H/N} = (I - \beta H/N) + O(N^{-2}).$$

We can now express $\langle x | \exp(-\beta H) | x \rangle$ as

$$\langle x | \exp(-\beta H) | x \rangle \approx \sum_{x_1, \dots, x_N} \langle x_1 | (I - \beta H/N) | x_2 \rangle \dots \langle x_N | (I - \beta H/N) | x_1 \rangle.$$

This method becomes exact as we take the limit $N \rightarrow \infty$, commonly referred to as the *continuous time limit* [42] and is widely used by Monte Carlo practitioners.

The approach just described is very similar to the famous "quantum to classical mapping" via the Suzuki-Trotter decomposition [11],[48],[44] which relies on decomposing $H = \sum_{j=1}^M H_j$ where $[H_i, H_j] \neq 0$. All operators grouped in H_j , mutually commute. Again, making use of the identity $e^{-\beta H} = [e^{-\beta H/N}]^N$ we introduce only a relatively small "Trotter" error ($\mathcal{O}(\Delta\tau^M)$) [49] when writing

$$\begin{aligned} \exp(-\Delta\tau H) &= \exp(-\Delta\tau \sum_j H_j) \approx \prod_{j=1}^M \exp(-\Delta\tau H_j) \\ \implies \exp(-\beta H) &\approx \prod_{i=1}^N \prod_{j=1}^M \exp(-\Delta\tau H_j^i), \end{aligned}$$

where $\Delta\tau = \beta/N$. Substituting this in the expression for the partition function and expectation value (inserting identity operators between each term in the double product) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \langle O \rangle &\approx \frac{\sum_{\{x\}} \langle x_{0,0} | O | x_{1,1} \rangle \prod_{i=1}^N \prod_{j=1}^M \langle x_{i,j} | e^{-\Delta\tau H_j^i} | x_{i,j+1} \rangle \delta_{(i,M+1),(i+1,0)} \delta_{(0,0),(N,M+1)}}{Z} \\ &\approx \frac{\sum_{\{x\}} \langle x_{0,0} | O | x_{1,1} \rangle Q(x_{0,0}, \dots, x_{N,M})}{Z}, \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{where } Q(x_{0,0}, \dots, x_{N,M}) = \prod_{i=1}^N \prod_{j=1}^M \langle x_{i,j} | e^{-\Delta\tau H_j^i} | x_{i,j+1} \rangle \delta_{(i,M+1),(i+1,0)}$$

$$Z \approx \sum_{\{x\}} \prod_{i=1}^N \prod_{j=1}^M \langle x_{i,j} | e^{-\Delta\tau H_j^i} | x_{i,j+1} \rangle \delta_{(i,M+1),(i+1,0)} \delta_{(1,1),(N,M+1)}.$$

Evaluating the partition function can therefore be thought of as summing over all configurations $\{x\}$ for which $x_{1,1} = x_{N,M+1}$ and $x_{i,j} \in \{0, 1\}^n$. This corresponds to a $n \times NM$ grid where we can imagine n qubits evolving over NM time (or Trotter) steps with periodic boundary conditions as depicted in figure 1.1. Each of the n slices, covering all NM time steps, is referred to as the *world-line* of that qubit. When evaluating the partition function these world-lines are *closed*, due to the periodic boundary conditions [17]. In contrast, the world-lines for $\langle O \rangle$ are "open" as there is no constrain on the boundaries. Since each H_j^i consists of simultaneously diagonalisable, local operators, the time complexity of evaluating matrix elements $\langle x_{i,j} | e^{-\Delta\tau H_j^i} | x_{i,j+1} \rangle$ goes as *poly*(n). Therefore, any term in the sum over configurations $\{x\}$ can be efficiently computed [48].

Having expressed $\langle O \rangle = \sum_{\{x\}} \langle x_{0,0} | O | x_{1,1} \rangle P(x_{0,0}, \dots, x_{N,M})$, where

$$P(x_{0,0}, \dots, x_{N,M}) = \frac{Q(x_{0,0}, \dots, x_{N,M})}{Z}$$

is a probability distribution when $Q(x_{0,0}, \dots, x_{N,M}) \geq 0 \forall \{x\}$, we can get an estimate of the expectation value by sampling $\langle x_{0,0} | O | x_{1,1} \rangle$ according to $P(x_{0,0}, \dots, x_{N,M})$. Note however, that for some Hamiltonians we have $Q(x_{0,0}, \dots, x_{N,M}) < 0$, in which case we say that the Hamiltonian has a sign problem [17],[48]. When the Hamiltonian is sign problem free and O is a local operator, we proceed as before, by setting up a Markov chain with stationary distribution $P(x_{0,0}, \dots, x_{N,M})$, employing the Metropolis algorithm. The issues of convergence and ergodicity discussed for classical Monte Carlo, will therefore carry over as well.

In our treatment of classical Monte Carlo we mentioned that evaluating the partition function requires a little more work. The situation is similar for the quantum partition function, as it cannot be expressed as the expectation of some random variable $\alpha(\mathbf{x})$ distributed according to $P(\mathbf{x})$ (i.e $Z = \sum_{\mathbf{x}} \alpha(\mathbf{x})P(\mathbf{x})$). One way to overcome this, albeit not the only one, uses the telescoping product technique by expressing $Z(\beta)$ as [35]

$$Z(\beta) = Z(0) \frac{Z(\beta_1)}{Z(\beta_0)} \cdots \frac{Z(\beta_k)}{Z(\beta_{k-1})},$$

where $0 = \beta_0 < \beta_1 < \dots < \beta_k = \beta$. Doing so, we avoid having to calculate the partition function at low temperature; instead only having to evaluate it for $T \rightarrow \infty$ and furthermore, be able to evaluate ratios $Z(\beta_i)/Z(\beta_{i-1})$. In contrast to the low temperature partition function, one can readily evaluate $Z(\beta \rightarrow 0)$ to be the total number of configurations of the system (for n qubits this is 2^n). Besides, the ratios of partition functions at different temperatures can be estimated using the fact that

$$\frac{Z(\beta_{i+1})}{Z(\beta_i)} = \sum_{\{x\}} \frac{e^{-\beta_{i+1}H(\mathbf{x})}}{e^{-\beta_i H(\mathbf{x})}} \times \frac{e^{-\beta_i H(\mathbf{x})}}{Z(\beta_i)}.$$

We can therefore define the random variable $Y_i(\mathbf{x}) = e^{(\beta_i - \beta_{i+1})H(\mathbf{x})}$ and obtain an estimate for $Z(\beta_{i+1})/Z(\beta_i)$ by the sample average of $Y_i(\mathbf{x})$, with respect to the distribution $\frac{e^{-\beta_i H(\mathbf{x})}}{Z(\beta_i)}$.

In the same way as we can have a sign problem when evaluating $\langle O \rangle$, we can also have a sign problem if $\frac{e^{-\beta_i H(\mathbf{x})}}{Z(\beta_i)} < 0$ for some configuration \mathbf{x} . If the Hamiltonian is sign problem free, we can obtain estimates for fractions $Z(\beta_{i+1})/Z(\beta_i)$ by sampling from the Gibbs distribution at β_i . This can be done in exactly the same fashion as in the evaluation of $\langle O \rangle$.

Figure 1.1: Checkerboard representation of partition function for 1-D Heisenberg XYZ Hamiltonian on $n = 6$ qubits. Vertical slices represents the "world-line" of the qubits. Each horizontal slice represents one Trotter step, with $|x_{i,j}\rangle = |\prod_{k=1}^6 x_{i,j}^k\rangle$ the full quantum state at step (i, j) where $i = 1, 2, 3$ and $j = 1, 2$. The bit corresponding to the state of the k^{th} qubit, at Trotter step (i, j) , is represented by $x_{i,j}^k$ (graphically represented by full/empty dots). The shaded plaquettes represent a matrix element $\langle x_{i,j}^k, x_{i,j}^{k+1} | e^{-\beta H_{k,k+1}} | x_{i,j+1}^k, x_{i,j+1}^{k+1} \rangle$.

To give a concrete example, let's consider the translationally invariant XYZ Heisenberg Hamiltonian with arbitrary coefficients, on a 1-D chain [48].

$$H = \sum_i \alpha_i^{XX} X_i X_{i+1} + \alpha_i^{YY} Y_i Y_{i+1} + \alpha_i^{ZZ} Z_i Z_{i+1}.$$

Using the Suzuki-Trotter decomposition we can split H into two terms H_a, H_b where H_a acts non trivially on all pairs of qubits defined by the even edges of the chain while H_b acts non trivially on all pairs defined by the odd edges.

$$H_a = \sum_{i=2k} H_{i,i+1}, \quad H_b = \sum_{i=2k+1} H_{i,i+1}, \quad k \in \mathbb{N}.$$

We can see that $[H_a, H_b] \neq 0$ but since no two terms in $H_a(H_b)$ share a qubit, we get that all Pauli operators in $H_a(H_b)$ mutually commute. Using the fact that for large N we can

approximate

$$\exp\left(-\frac{\beta H}{N}\right) = \exp\left(-\frac{\beta(H_a + H_b)}{N}\right) \approx \exp\left(-\frac{\beta H_a}{N}\right) \exp\left(-\frac{\beta H_b}{N}\right),$$

we can express $\langle O \rangle = \text{Tr}[Oe^{-\beta H}]/Z$ as

$$\begin{aligned} \langle O \rangle &= \frac{1}{Z} \sum_{x_{1,1}, \dots, x_{N,2}} \langle x_{1,1} | \hat{O} | x_{1,2} \rangle \langle x_{1,2} | \exp(-\beta H_a/N) | x_{2,1} \rangle \langle x_{2,1} | \exp(-\beta H_b/N) | x_{2,2} \rangle \dots \\ &\quad \langle x_{N,1} | \exp(-\beta H_a/N) | x_{N,2} \rangle \langle x_{N,2} | \exp(-\beta H_b/N) | x_{1,1} \rangle \\ &= \frac{1}{Z} \sum_{x_{1,1}, \dots, x_{N,2}} \langle x_{1,1} | \hat{O} | x_{1,2} \rangle \langle x_{1,2} | \prod_{i=2k} e^{-\beta H_{i \ i+1}/N} | x_{2,1} \rangle \langle x_{2,1} | \prod_{i=2k+1} e^{-\beta H_{i \ i+1}/N} | x_{2,2} \rangle \dots \\ &\quad \langle x_{N,1} | \prod_{i=2k} e^{-\beta H_{i \ i+1}/N} | x_{N,2} \rangle \langle x_{N,2} | \prod_{i=2k+1} e^{-\beta H_{i \ i+1}/N} | x_{1,1} \rangle. \end{aligned}$$

As each $H_{i \ i+1}$ acts locally on a pair of qubits, it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \langle x_{i,j} | \prod_{i=2k} e^{-\beta H_{i \ i+1}/N} | x_{k,l} \rangle &= \langle x_{i,j}^2 x_{i,j}^3 | e^{-\beta H_{23}/N} | x_{k,l}^2 x_{k,l}^3 \rangle \langle x_{i,j}^4 x_{i,j}^5 | e^{-\beta H_{45}/N} | x_{k,l}^4 x_{k,l}^5 \rangle \dots \\ \langle x_{i,j} | \prod_{i=2k+1} e^{-\beta H_{i \ i+1}/N} | x_{k,l} \rangle &= \langle x_{i,j}^1 x_{i,j}^2 | e^{-\beta H_{12}/N} | x_{k,l}^1 x_{k,l}^2 \rangle \langle x_{i,j}^3 x_{i,j}^4 | e^{-\beta H_{34}/N} | x_{k,l}^3 x_{k,l}^4 \rangle \dots \end{aligned}$$

where $x_{i,j}, x_{k,l} \in \{0, 1\}^n$ while $x_{i,j}^p \in \{0, 1\}^2$. We can therefore evaluate the product

$$\langle x_{1,2} | \exp(-\beta H_a/N) | x_{2,1} \rangle \langle x_{2,1} | \exp(-\beta H_b/N) | x_{2,2} \rangle \dots \langle x_{2N} | \exp(-\beta H_b/N) | x_{1,1} \rangle$$

efficiently. Expanding $e^{-\beta H_{i \ i+1}/N}$ to first order, we get.

$$e^{-\beta H_{i \ i+1}/N} = \begin{bmatrix} I - \beta \alpha_{i \ i+1}^{ZZ}/N & 0 & 0 & -\beta(\alpha_{i \ i+1}^{XX} - \alpha_{i \ i+1}^{YY})/N \\ 0 & I + \beta \alpha_{i \ i+1}^{ZZ}/N & -\beta(\alpha_{i \ i+1}^{XX} + \alpha_{i \ i+1}^{YY})/N & 0 \\ 0 & -\beta(\alpha_{i \ i+1}^{XX} + \alpha_{i \ i+1}^{YY})/N & I + \beta \alpha_{i \ i+1}^{ZZ}/N & 0 \\ -\beta(\alpha_{i \ i+1}^{XX} - \alpha_{i \ i+1}^{YY})/N & 0 & 0 & I - \beta \alpha_{i \ i+1}^{ZZ}/N \end{bmatrix}$$

Due to the periodic boundary conditions, the partition function can be expressed as the sum over terms representable in a checkerboard diagram, see figure 1.1. In the checkerboard representation the non-zero matrix elements of $e^{-\beta H_{i \ i+1}/N}$ can be interpreted as allowed moves on coloured plaquettes (see figure 1.2) with the weight of the corresponding configuration given by the product of the weights of coloured plaquettes. As we saw in the example of the Ising Hamiltonian in the previous section, the most elementary moves we can propose are local updates. In the classical example these corresponded to single spin flips, while here they correspond to updating plaquettes. As before, if the energy of the system is lowered as a consequence of the update, the move is accepted with certainty. Moves leading to a configuration with higher energy are accepted with probability depending on the relative energy difference.

Figure 1.2: Allowed moves on each plaquette with its associated weight. At each step in the Metropolis algorithm we choose randomly one or more (depending on the scheme used) of the plaquettes to update it-with equal probability-to one of the 8 allowed plaquettes presented.

1.3 Sign problem in Quantum Monte Carlo

As we have mentioned before, $Q(x_{0,0}, \dots, x_{N,M})$ is in general a quasi-probability distribution. This can be problematic as we cannot sample according to negative probabilities. Before showing how one can, in principle, circumvent the issue of negative probabilities, let us first define the notion of stoquastified Hamiltonians.

Definition 5 (Stoquastified Hamiltonian). *Given a Hamiltonian H its stoquastified counterpart \tilde{H} is defined as:*

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{H}_{xy} &= -|H_{xy}| \quad \forall x \neq y \\ \tilde{H}_{xx} &= H_{xx}\end{aligned}$$

In the context of fermionic systems suffering from the sign problem, the stoquastified Hamiltonian can be interpreted as the Hamiltonian of the equivalent bosonic system [17]. The most direct way to deal with the quasi-probability distribution is to absorb the sign of $Q(\mathbf{x})$ in the observable.

$$Q(\mathbf{x}) = \text{sgn}(Q(\mathbf{x}))|Q(\mathbf{x})|$$

we can transform

$$\langle O \rangle_H \approx \frac{\sum_{\mathbf{x}} O(\mathbf{x})Q(\mathbf{x})}{\sum_{\mathbf{x}} Q(\mathbf{x})} = \frac{\sum_{\mathbf{x}} O(\mathbf{x}) \text{sgn}(Q(\mathbf{x}))|Q(\mathbf{x})| / \sum_{\mathbf{x}} |Q(\mathbf{x})|}{\sum_{\mathbf{x}} \text{sgn}(Q(\mathbf{x}))|Q(\mathbf{x})| / \sum_{\mathbf{x}} |Q(\mathbf{x})|} = \frac{\langle O(\mathbf{x})\text{sgn}(Q(\mathbf{x})) \rangle_{\tilde{H}}}{\langle \text{sgn}(Q(\mathbf{x})) \rangle_{\tilde{H}}}$$

$$Z \approx \sum_{\mathbf{x}} Q(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{\sum_{\mathbf{x}} \text{sgn}(Q(\mathbf{x})) |Q(\mathbf{x})| \sum_{\mathbf{x}} |Q(\mathbf{x})|}{\sum_{\mathbf{x}} |Q(\mathbf{x})|} = \sum_{\mathbf{x}} \text{sgn}(Q(\mathbf{x})) \tilde{Z} \times \frac{|Q(\mathbf{x})|}{\tilde{Z}} = \langle \text{sgn}(Q(\mathbf{x})) \tilde{Z} \rangle_{\tilde{H}},$$

where \tilde{Z} is the partition function for the stoquastified Hamiltonian \tilde{H} and $\langle \dots \rangle_{\tilde{H}}$ the expectation value with respect to \tilde{H} . We have successfully expressed the expectation value with respect to some quasi-probability distribution, in terms of expectation values with respect to a regular distribution and seemingly avoided the sign problem. However, note that in order to evaluate $\langle O \rangle_H$ we need to calculate $\langle O(\mathbf{x}) \text{sgn}(Q(\mathbf{x})) \rangle_{\tilde{H}}$ and $\langle \text{sgn}(Q(\mathbf{x})) \rangle_{\tilde{H}}$ independently. Furthermore, $\langle \text{sgn}(Q(\mathbf{x})) \rangle_{\tilde{H}}$ can be exponentially small, for example if $\text{sgn}(Q(\mathbf{x})) = +1$ for about half the configurations \mathbf{x} . Let there be $2k$, with $k = \mathcal{O}(1)$, more configurations with $\text{sgn}(Q(\mathbf{x})) = -1$ than those with $\text{sgn}(Q(\mathbf{x})) = +1$. In this case we get $\langle \text{sgn}(Q(\mathbf{x})) \rangle_{\tilde{H}} = -\frac{2k}{2^n}$. Similarly, one can show an inverse exponential dependence (in β) of $\langle \text{sgn}(Q(\mathbf{x})) \rangle_{\tilde{H}}$:

$$\langle \text{sgn}(Q(\mathbf{x})) \rangle_{\tilde{H}} = \frac{\text{Tr}[e^{-\beta H}]}{\text{Tr}[e^{-\beta \tilde{H}}]} = \frac{Z}{\tilde{Z}} \propto e^{-\beta(F_{\tilde{Z}} - F_Z)},$$

since the free energy is given by $F = -\beta^{-1} \log(Z)$. Thus $\langle \text{sgn}(Q(\mathbf{x})) \rangle_{\tilde{H}}$ becomes exponentially small with system size and β . Chebyshev's inequality tells us that the deviation of the sample mean from the expectation value ϵ is bounded by

$$\epsilon \leq \sqrt{\frac{\text{Var}(X)}{m(1-p)}},$$

where $0 \leq p \leq 1$, m is the number of samples taken and X is an i.i.d random variable [17]. Since $\langle \text{sgn}(Q(\mathbf{x})) \rangle_{\tilde{H}}$ is exponentially small in system size and β , one would need to take an exponentially large number of samples, m , to achieve a reasonable relative error. Thus we cannot, efficiently, get any usable approximation for $\langle O \rangle_H$ at low temperatures and/or large systems, if the Hamiltonian suffers from the sign problem. We conclude that we have a sign problem when $\langle \text{sgn}(Q(\mathbf{x})) \rangle_{\tilde{H}} < 1$ i.e when the partition function of H and its stoquastified counterpart \tilde{H} are not equal. The severity of the sign problem will depend on the temperature and system size we are considering.

1.3.1 Avoiding the sign problem

Clearly a sufficient condition for avoiding the sign problem is that the system's Hamiltonian satisfies [9]

$$\langle x | e^{-\beta H} | y \rangle \geq 0 \quad \forall x, y \in \{0, 1\}^n$$

However, it is evident that this is by no means a *necessary* condition for non-negativity of $Q(x_{0,0}, \dots, x_{N,M})$. Using the checkerboard representation for the partition function in the XYZ Heisenberg example, we can see that any valid configuration will have the same number of plaquettes of type (a) and (b) and the same number of plaquettes of type (c) and

(d) (see figure 1.2) in order to satisfy the boundary conditions [48]. Another approach for avoiding an apparent sign problem has been proposed recently [18],[19] where the author suggests a regrouping of the terms being summed, in such a way that the regrouped terms are all non-negative.

These problem-specific arguments have been developed to show that the quasi-probability distributions $Q(x_{0,0}, \dots, x_{N,M}) / \sum_{\{x\}} Q(x_{0,0}, \dots, x_{N,M})$ are in fact ordinary probability distributions. They achieve this by exploiting some details specific to the Monte Carlo method used, in conjunction with the Hamiltonian under consideration, and can therefore not be straightforwardly generalised to other methods and/or Hamiltonians. We will see that there is a more systematic way in order to avoid the sign problem for a large class of Hamiltonians. Chapter four will be devoted entirely to this approach, showing that the two classes of Hamiltonians mentioned (among others) can be cast in a sign problem free form in an efficient manner.

1.4 Summary

We have formally introduced the Monte Carlo method both in the classical, as well as the quantum setting, giving the necessary conditions for the method to converge. We discussed the sign problem in the context of Quantum Monte Carlo method, showing under what circumstances it can be avoided. In the next chapter we will describe the class of *stoquastic* Hamiltonians [9] which, based on our observations, is always sign problem free and thus, is amenable to Monte Carlo simulations.

Chapter 2

Stoquastic Hamiltonians

Despite the Monte Carlo method being a heuristic tool and in most cases no proven bounds on its run-time exist, it has nevertheless shown to be successful in producing accurate results. The presence of a sign problem, however, can render the method ineffective, and as such it is vital to have a systematic approach for deciding when a given Hamiltonian is sign problem free. We will approach this problem by focusing on the Hamiltonian itself, introducing the class of stoquastic Hamiltonians and discussing some of their main properties. Despite their idiosyncratic definition, stoquastic Hamiltonians are relatively common. We will only treat qubit Hamiltonians but it has been shown that also a great number of bosonic systems are stoquastic. As discussed in [9] Bose-Einstein condensates, the class of bosonic Hubbard models as well as flux-qubit systems are all examples of stoquastic Hamiltonians.

2.1 Basic definitions and preliminary results

Stoquastic Hamiltonians were first introduced by Bravyi, DiVincenzo, Oliveira and Terhal in [9] where they study the difficulty of finding the ground energy of such Hamiltonians. As we saw in our analysis of the world-line Monte Carlo method, a sufficient condition for a Hamiltonian to be sign problem free is

$$\langle x | e^{-\beta H/N} | y \rangle \geq 0 \quad \forall x, y \in \{0, 1\}^n.$$

This directly implies that the quasi-probability distribution

$$\frac{\prod_{i=1}^N \langle x_i | e^{-\beta H/N} | x_{i+1} \rangle \delta_{x_{N+1}, x_0}}{Z},$$

is in fact an ordinary probability distribution from which we can sample using MCMC.

Stoquastic Hamiltonians are defined in such a way as to ensure that $e^{-\beta H/N}$ is a non-negative matrix in the computational basis.

Proposition 5. *We have*

$$\langle x | e^{-\beta H} | y \rangle \geq 0 \quad \forall x, y \in \{0, 1\}^n, \quad \forall \beta,$$

if

$$\langle x | H | y \rangle \leq 0 \quad \forall x \neq y$$

Proof. [2] Assume H is such that $\langle x | H | y \rangle \leq 0 \quad \forall x \neq y$ and let C be some constant such that $\langle x | (-\beta H + C) | y \rangle \geq 0 \quad \forall x, y \in \{0, 1\}^n$. It follows that

$$\langle x | e^{-\beta H + C} | y \rangle = \langle x | \sum_k \frac{(-\beta H + C)^k}{k!} | y \rangle \geq 0 \quad \forall x, y.$$

Writing $e^{-C} = p > 0$ we get

$$\langle x | e^{-\beta H} | y \rangle = \langle x | p e^{-\beta H + C} | y \rangle \geq 0 \quad \forall x, y$$

□

We can therefore define a stoquastic Hamiltonian with respect to the sign of its off-diagonal matrix elements. Whether a Hamiltonian is stoquastic or not, will depend on the basis we choose to represent it in, something we will discuss in detail in chapter four.

Definition 6 (Global stoquasticity [26]). *A real, Hermitian Hamiltonian H on n qubits is globally stoquastic in the computational basis $\{|x\rangle\}$ if*

$$\langle x | H | y \rangle \leq 0 \quad \forall x \neq y \in \{0, 1\}^n$$

Global stoquasticity is therefore a sufficient condition for avoiding the sign problem. Throughout this thesis we will be dealing with k -local Hamiltonians $H = \sum_i H_i$. We therefore, also define the notion of local or term-wise stoquasticity.

Definition 7 (Local stoquasticity[9]). *A real, Hermitian Hamiltonian H on n qubits is k' -locally stoquastic in the computational basis $\{|x\rangle\}$, if there exists a decomposition into k' -local terms $H = \sum_i H_i$ such that*

$$\langle x | H_i | y \rangle \leq 0 \quad \forall x \neq y \in \{0, 1\}^n.$$

Here H_i acts non-trivially on a subset of at most k' qubits.

As real, Hermitian matrices are symmetric, in the mathematics literature, stoquastic matrices correspond to symmetric Z-matrices

Definition 8 (Symmetric Z-matrix[27]). *A real, symmetric matrix M in a basis \mathcal{B} is called a symmetric Z-matrix if it has non-positive off diagonal matrix elements.*

Clearly, every k' -locally stoquastic Hamiltonian is globally stoquastic for any k' , since the summand on the right hand side of $\langle x | H | y \rangle = \sum_i \langle x | H_i | y \rangle$ is non-positive $\forall x \neq y, \forall i$ if H is locally stoquastic. However, the question whether, for some k -local, globally stoquastic Hamiltonian there exists a k -locally stoquastic decomposition, is a less trivial one. Indeed, we will see that in some cases a given Hamiltonian only becomes locally stoquastic once a $(k' > k)$ -local decomposition is considered.

2.1.1 Preliminary results

Non-negativity of the ground state

The most well known property of stoquastic Hamiltonians is the fact that their ground states have non-negative amplitudes. This can be seen from the fact that the ground state is reached at zero temperature ($\beta \rightarrow \infty$)

$$\lim_{\beta \rightarrow \infty} e^{-\beta H} = |\psi\rangle \langle \psi| = \rho_g.$$

In conjunction with Proposition 5 we have $\langle x | \rho_g | y \rangle \geq 0 \forall x, y \in \{0, 1\}^n$. Alternatively, the non-negativity of the ground state can also be seen from the fact that $G = (I - CH)$ is a non-negative matrix if C a small constant, inverse proportional to the norm of H . The highest eigenstate of G corresponds to the ground state of H ($|\psi\rangle$) and using the Perron-Frobenius Theorem [20] we conclude that [9]

$$|\psi\rangle = \sum_i \alpha_i |x_i\rangle \quad \text{such that } \alpha_i \geq 0 \quad \forall i.$$

We now turn our attention to the relation between the two definitions of stoquasticity.

2.2 Local vs global stoquasticity

Local \iff global stoquasticity for two-local Hamiltonians

Proposition 6. *Given a real two-local Hamiltonian H on n qubits, the Hamiltonian is two-locally stoquastic if and only if it is globally stoquastic [26].*

This was first stated without proof in [9]. Here I present an original proof which has also appeared in [26].

Proof. The one direction of the proof is trivial to show. If the Hamiltonian is locally stoquastic, i.e there exists a decomposition $H = \sum_{i < j} H_{ij}$ such that H_{ij} is real and $\forall x \neq y, \langle x | H_{ij} | y \rangle \leq 0$, then H is real and $\forall x \neq y, \langle x | H | y \rangle = \sum_{i,j} \langle x | H_{ij} | y \rangle \leq 0$. For the other direction, since H is Hermitian and real, $H = H^\top$. Therefore every Pauli operator P in the Pauli expansion of H must satisfy $P = P^\top$, and so H does not contain any Pauli operators with odd numbers of Y terms. We can group the Pauli operators in the expansion of the Hamiltonian into three sets, according to the number of bits each Pauli flips. Let $d_H(x, y)$ denote the Hamming distance between bit strings x and y , with $\langle x | H^{(m)} | y \rangle = 0$ whenever $d_H(x, y) \neq m$. Since H in this case is two-local, there can be three sets of Paulis for which $\langle x | P | y \rangle \neq 0$ corresponding to $d_H(x, y) \in \{0, 1, 2\}$ and hence

$$H = H^{(0)} + H^{(1)} + H^{(2)}$$

Here $H^{(0)}$ contains all terms which are diagonal (i.e., terms of the form ZI, IZ and ZZ), $H^{(1)}$ contains all terms that flip one bit (i.e., of the form XZ, ZX, XI, IX), and $H^{(2)}$

contains all terms that flip two bits (of the form XX and YY). From the definition of locally/globally stoquastic Hamiltonians, there is no particular condition which has to be fulfilled for the diagonal group $H^{(0)}$, and so we ignore it. Since the positions of non-zero off-diagonal matrix elements of $H^{(1)}$ and $H^{(2)}$ differ, we can treat them independently, demanding that $\forall x \neq y \langle x | H^{(1)} | y \rangle \leq 0$ and $\langle x | H^{(2)} | y \rangle \leq 0$ for the Hamiltonian to be globally stoquastic.

For any potential decomposition into local terms, $H = \sum_{i < j} H_{ij}$, we can similarly group terms according to the Hamming distance between bits giving non-zero matrix elements. Thus we write

$$H_{ij} = \sum_{i < j} \sum_{m=0}^2 H_{ij}^{(m)},$$

grouping diagonal, one-qubit flipping, and two-qubit flipping terms. Since $H^{(m)}$ contains all terms which flip m -qubits

$$H^{(m)} = \sum_{i < j} H_{ij}^{(m)}$$

In the case of $m = 2$, $H_{ij}^{(2)}$ and $H_{wx}^{(2)}$ are non-zero at different off-diagonal positions when $i, j \neq w, x$, and so $\forall x \neq y \langle x | H^{(2)} | y \rangle \leq 0$ implies $\forall x \neq y, \forall i < j, \langle x | H_{ij}^{(2)} | y \rangle \leq 0$.

In the case of $m = 1$, $H_{ij}^{(1)}$ and $H_{wx}^{(1)}$ may both be non-zero on the same off-diagonal position when either one of the indexes i, j equals one of the indexes w, x . We can write

$$H^{(1)} = \sum_{i, j: i < j} [a_{ij}^{XZ} X_i Z_j + a_{ij}^{ZX} Z_i X_j] + \sum_i a_i^X X_i$$

By writing out matrix elements, one can show that

$$\forall x \neq y, \langle x | H^{(1)} | y \rangle \leq 0 \Rightarrow a_i^X + \sum_{j: j > i} \Delta_j a_{ij}^{XZ} + \sum_{w: w < i} \Delta_w a_{wi}^{ZX} \leq 0,$$

for all choices of sign-patterns $\Delta_j = \pm 1$. This implies that

$$a_i^X \leq - \left(\sum_{j: j > i} |a_{ij}^{XZ}| + \sum_{w: w < i} |a_{wi}^{ZX}| \right). \quad (2.1)$$

Local terms $H_{ij}^{(1)}$ will be of the form:

$$H_{ij}^{(1)} = a_{ij}^{XZ} X_i Z_j + a_{ij}^{ZX} Z_i X_j + a_{ij}^{XI} X_i I_j + a_{ij}^{IX} I_i Z_j,$$

where the coefficients a_{ij}^{XI}, a_{ij}^{IX} can be freely chosen up to the overall constraint

$$a_i^X = \sum_{j: j > i} a_{ij}^{XI} + \sum_{w: w < i} a_{wi}^{IX}.$$

Clearly, if Equation 2.1 holds, then one can always, non-uniquely, distribute a_i^X into a sum over a_{ij}^{XI} (for $j > i$) and a_{wi}^{IX} (for $w < i$) such that each $a_{ij}^{XI} \leq -|a_{ij}^{XZ}|$ and each $a_{wi}^{IX} \leq -|a_{wi}^{ZX}|$. Hence, such an allocation constitutes a decomposition of the globally stoquastic Hamiltonian where each term is stoquastic. \square

Local stoquasticity for three-local Hamiltonians

For ($k \geq 3$)-local Hamiltonians the situation is different as we can have Hamiltonians which are globally but not locally stoquastic. This was first mentioned without proof in [9]. We will first show that this is indeed the case through an example courtesy of Sergey Bravyi and then analyse the situation in general.

Proposition 7. *There exist ($k \geq 3$)-local, globally stoquastic Hamiltonians on n qubits, which are not k -locally stoquastic.*

Proof. Given a graph $G = (V, E)$, consider the three-local Hamiltonian $H = X_1 \otimes (E_0 - H_{\text{Ising}})$ on n qubits, where $E_0 = \min_x [\langle x | H_{\text{Ising}} | x \rangle]$ is the ground energy of H_{Ising} and $x \in \{0, 1\}^{n-1}$. Here

$$H_{\text{Ising}} = \sum_{(i,j) \in E} J_{ij} Z_i Z_j,$$

with $J_{ij} \in \{-1, 0, +1\}$. H is globally stoquastic since

$$\langle x | (E_0 - H_{\text{Ising}}) | y \rangle = \delta_{x,y} (\min_x [\langle x | H_{\text{Ising}} | x \rangle] - \langle x | H_{\text{Ising}} | x \rangle) \leq 0 \quad \forall x \in \{0, 1\}^{n-1},$$

from where it follows that $\langle x | H | y \rangle \leq 0 \quad \forall x \neq y \in \{0, 1\}^n$. The classical Hamiltonian H_{Ising} does not admit a two-local frustration-free decomposition if $E_0 > -|E|$. This means that there does not exist any two-local decomposition for which the ground state $|\psi_g\rangle$ of H_{Ising} simultaneously minimises the energy of all two-local terms (there is at least one pair $(i, j) \in E$ for which we have $J_{ij} Z_i Z_j |\psi_g\rangle = +1 |\psi_g\rangle$).

We can group the Pauli terms in any Hamiltonian with respect to the bits they flip

$$H = \sum_x H(x),$$

where $x \in \{0, 1\}^n$ labels the position of the bits being flipped. Each term $H(x)$ has different non-zero off-diagonal elements and therefore can be treated independently. Hence, if H is globally stoquastic, each $H(x)$ is a symmetric Z -matrix in the computational basis. Consider now a decomposition into local terms $H = \sum_x H(x) = \sum_x \sum_{\mathbf{i}} H_{\mathbf{i}}(x)$, where each $H_{\mathbf{i}}(x)$ acts on a subset of at most three qubits labeled by the triple \mathbf{i} . As each $H_{\mathbf{i}}(x)$ has different non-zero off-diagonal matrix elements, for H to be three-locally stoquastic, each $H_{\mathbf{i}}(x)$ needs to be a symmetric Z -matrix in the computational basis.

For the Hamiltonian under consideration, the grouping results in a single set $H = X_1 \otimes (E_0 - H_{\text{Ising}}) = H(10\dots 00)$. For H to be locally stoquastic there needs to exist a decomposition

$$H(10\dots 00) = \sum_{\mathbf{i}} H_{\mathbf{i}}(10\dots 00) = \sum_{i < j} X_1 \otimes H_{ij}(0\dots 0),$$

such that $H_{ij}(0\dots 0)$ is a symmetric Z -matrix for all pairs (i, j) . The most general form $H_{ij}(0\dots 0)$ can take is given by

$$H_{ij}(0\dots 0) = \alpha_{ij}^I I_{ij} + \alpha_{ij}^{IZ} Z_j + \alpha_{ij}^{ZI} Z_i + J_{ij} Z_i Z_j,$$

with the restrictions $\sum_{i<j} \alpha_{ij}^I = E_0$, $\sum_{i:i<j} \alpha_{ij}^{IZ} = 0 \forall j$ and $\sum_{j:j>i} \alpha_{ij}^{ZI} = 0 \forall i$. Therefore the condition for H_{ij} to be a symmetric Z -matrix becomes:

$$\alpha_{ij}^I \leq \min_{\Delta_i, \Delta_j} [-\Delta_j \alpha_{ij}^{IZ} - \Delta_i \alpha_{ij}^{ZI} - \Delta_i \Delta_j J_{ij}] \leq -1.$$

This cannot be satisfied for H_{Ising} , which does not admit any two-local frustration-free decomposition, as it would require $\sum_{i<j} \alpha_{ij}^I \leq -|E|$ (in contradiction to the constraint $\sum_{i<j} \alpha_{ij}^I = E_0 > -E$). □

As we saw, the discrepancy between the two notions of stoquasticity arises when the Ising Hamiltonian in $H = X_1 \otimes (E_0 - H_{\text{Ising}})$ does not admit a two-local frustration free decomposition. In order to generalise this, let us define the following notion.

Definition 9. *A k -local Hamiltonian H , admits a k' -locally unrestricted decomposition, if there exists a k' -local decomposition $H = \sum_{\mathbf{i}} H_{\mathbf{i}}$, where $H_{\mathbf{i}}$ acts non trivially on a subset of at most k' qubits (defined by the k' -tuple \mathbf{i}) such that the smallest matrix elements of H and of all $H_{\mathbf{i}}$ occur at the same position in the canonical basis representation. Let u_{\min}, v_{\min} be such that*

$$\begin{aligned} \langle u_{\min} | H | v_{\min} \rangle &= \min_{u,v} [\langle u | H | v \rangle] \\ \text{we have } \forall \mathbf{i} \langle u_{\min} | H_{\mathbf{i}} | v_{\min} \rangle &= \min_{u,v} [\langle u | H_{\mathbf{i}} | v \rangle] \end{aligned}$$

where $u \neq v \in \{0, 1\}^n$. If either H or some $H_{\mathbf{i}}$ do not have a unique smallest matrix element, it is understood that it is sufficient for the above condition to hold for a particular choice.

This is similar to the notion of frustration in Ising Hamiltonians. As we have seen, when an Ising Hamiltonian is frustrated, the ground state spin configuration does not constitute a ground state configuration for all two-local terms $J_{ij} Z_i Z_j$. According to our definition, it is easy to see that every Hamiltonian admits a n -local unrestricted decomposition, as there exists an n -local decomposition with only one term, namely the full Hamiltonian. Therefore, there must exist a transition point, i.e some $2 \leq k \leq n$ for which the Hamiltonian admits a k' -locally unrestricted decomposition $\forall k' \geq k$ but does not admit unrestricted, k'' -local decompositions for any $k'' < k$.

To get some insight about where this transition point occurs, let us begin by grouping the terms in the Hamiltonian according to the bits they flip

$$H = \sum_x H(x) \quad \forall x \in \{0, 1\}^n.$$

For every $H(x)$ we define

$$\tilde{H}(x) := H(x) - \alpha(x) \bigotimes_{i=1}^n X_i^{x_i}, \quad (2.2)$$

with x_i the i^{th} bit of x and $\alpha(x)$ the coefficient of the Pauli $\bigotimes_{i=1}^n X_i^{x_i}$ occurring in $H(x)$ (if no such term is present in $H(x)$, this implies that $\alpha(x) = 0$). Formally we can define $\alpha(x) = \text{Tr}[H(x) \bigotimes_{i=1}^n X_i^{x_i}]$. For example, consider the two-local Hamiltonian on 4 qubits $H = X_1 X_2 + Y_1 Y_2 + X_1 Z_2 + 2X_1 + Y_1 Y_3 + 3X_4$. According to our definition $H(1100) = X_1 X_2 + Y_1 Y_2$, $H(1000) = 2X_1 + X_1 Z_2$, $H(1010) = Y_1 Y_3$ and $H(0001) = 3X_4$ with $H(x) = 0$ for all remaining 4-bit strings x . Respectively we have $\alpha(1100) = 1$, $\alpha(1000) = 2$, $\alpha(0001) = 3$ and $\alpha(x) = 0$ for all remainin 4-bit strings x .

If H is globally stoquastic, by definition we have

$$\forall x \quad \langle u | H(x) | v \rangle \leq 0 \implies \langle u | \alpha(x) \bigotimes_{i=1}^n X_i^{x_i} | v \rangle \leq - \langle u | \tilde{H}(x) | v \rangle \quad \forall u \neq v, \forall x.$$

It follows that $\alpha(x) \leq \min_{u,v} [\langle u | -\tilde{H}(x) | v \rangle]$ is satisfied for all x . Alternatively the last relation can also be written as $\alpha(x) \leq -\max_{u,v} [\langle u | \tilde{H}(x) | v \rangle]$. We will choose to use the former way to represent the condition for global stoquasticity, as it will allow us to connect the existence of a stoquastic decomposition to the notion of unrestricted decompositions. Considering a k' -local decomposition of H , each $H(x) = \sum_{\mathbf{i}} H_{\mathbf{i}}(x)$ where $H_{\mathbf{i}}(x)$ acts non trivially on a different subset of k' qubits, defined by the k' -tuple \mathbf{i} . Hence for H to be k' -locally stoquastic, there has to exist a decomposition such that $\langle u | H_{\mathbf{i}}(x) | v \rangle \leq 0 \forall u \neq v, \forall \mathbf{i}$. Again we associate to each $H_{\mathbf{i}}$ an operator

$$\tilde{H}_{\mathbf{i}}(x) = H_{\mathbf{i}}(x) - \alpha_{\mathbf{i}}(x) \bigotimes_{i=1}^n X_i^{x_i},$$

where x_i is the i^{th} bit of x , such that $\sum_{\mathbf{i}} \alpha_{\mathbf{i}}(x) = \alpha(x)$. It follows that the condition for the Hamiltonian to be locally stoquastic is:

$$\langle u | H_{\mathbf{i}}(x) | v \rangle \leq 0 \implies \alpha_{\mathbf{i}}(x) \leq \min_{u,v} [\langle u | -\tilde{H}_{\mathbf{i}}(x) | v \rangle] \quad \forall x, \forall \mathbf{i} \quad \forall u \neq v \quad (2.3)$$

$$\text{such that } \sum_{\mathbf{i}} \alpha_{\mathbf{i}}(x) = \alpha(x) \quad (2.4)$$

Consider H being "barely" globally stoquastic, i.e for some x the condition for global stoquasticity is just satisfied ($\alpha(x) = \min_{u,v} [\langle u | -\tilde{H}(x) | v \rangle]$). If $-\tilde{H}(x)$ admits a k' -local unrestricted decomposition $\forall x$, it follows that

$$\sum_{\mathbf{i}} (\min_{u,v} [\langle u | -\tilde{H}_{\mathbf{i}} | v \rangle]) = \min_{u,v} [\langle u | -\tilde{H}(x) | v \rangle].$$

Therefore conditions 2.3 and 2.4 can be satisfied by choosing each $\alpha_{\mathbf{i}}(x) = \min_{u,v} [\langle u | -\tilde{H}_{\mathbf{i}}(x) | v \rangle]$.

If H is globally stoquastic with $\alpha(x) < \min_{u,v} [\langle u | -\tilde{H}(x) | v \rangle]$ for all x , it is clear that we can always choose $\alpha_{\mathbf{i}}(x) = \min_{u,v} [\langle u | -\tilde{H}_{\mathbf{i}}(x) | v \rangle] - \gamma_{\mathbf{i}}$ where $\gamma_{\mathbf{i}} \geq 0$, such that 2.3 and 2.4 are satisfied.

We therefore conclude that finding the minimum locality for which it is *guaranteed* that there exists some stoquastic decomposition for a globally stoquastic Hamiltonian, reduces to finding the minimum locality k_{\min} for which $-\tilde{H}(x)$ admits an unrestricted decomposition for all x .

2.2.1 Two-local restricted Hamiltonians which are three-local unrestricted

We will illustrate this through the analysis of Hamiltonians of the type $H = X_1 \otimes (E - H_{\text{Ising}})$, giving examples where this transition point can be found analytically. For this Hamiltonian, $\min_{u,v} [\langle u | -\tilde{H}(10\dots 0) | v \rangle] = E_0$ where E_0 is the ground energy of H_{Ising} , while $\min_{u,v} [\langle u | -\tilde{H}(x) | v \rangle] = 0$ for all other $x \in \{0, 1\}^n$. Therefore H admits a $(k + 1)$ -local unrestricted decomposition (and hence is $(k + 1)$ -locally stoquastic) if H_{Ising} admits a k -local frustration-free decomposition. As we mentioned earlier, this means that there exists a decomposition $H_{\text{Ising}} = \sum_i H_i$ where each H_i is k -local and the ground state of H_{Ising} simultaneously minimises the energy of all terms H_i .

To illustrate the concept of frustration-free Hamiltonians, given H_{Ising} , construct a graph $G = (V, E)$. Each vertex represents a qubit and each edge between v_i, v_j is weighted by J_{ij} , representing the interaction $J_{ij}Z_iZ_j$. The ground state then corresponds to an assignment $v_i = \pm 1$ for all $v_i \in V$. The assignment is chosen such that $\sum_{(v_i, v_j) \in E} J_{ij}v_iv_j$ (i.e the energy corresponding to the state $|x\rangle$) is minimised. All edges for which $J_{ij}v_iv_j = -1$ are said to be satisfied while, those for which $J_{ij}v_iv_j = +1$ are said to be unsatisfied [5]. The mapping from this binary assignment $v_i = \pm 1$ to the ground state of H_{Ising} , $|x\rangle$, can be seen as $v_i = 1 \rightarrow x_i = 0$ while $v_i = -1 \rightarrow x_i = 1$ where x_i is the i^{th} bit of x . Graphically we will represent the ground state by the edge-2-coloured graph $G = (V, E)$ where the two colours correspond to satisfied/unsatisfied edges. The minimal example of a frustrated Ising Hamiltonian requires three coupled qubits i.e

$$H_{\text{Ising}} = Z_1Z_2 + Z_1Z_3 + Z_2Z_3$$

Figure 2.1: Graphical representation of the ground state $|001\rangle \implies v_1 = 1, v_2 = 1, v_3 = -1$ of $H_{\text{Ising}} = Z_1Z_2 + Z_1Z_3 + Z_2Z_3$. The edge (v_1, v_2) is unsatisfied as $J_{12}v_1v_2 = +1$.

Clearly, for the triangular graph and $J_{12} = J_{13} = J_{23} = +1$, we can check that there is no way to have all three edges satisfied and as such the Hamiltonian is frustrated. It is no surprise that H_{Ising} admits a three-local frustration-free decomposition, as such a decomposition consists of a single term, namely the global Hamiltonian itself. In order to show that the existence of such a frustration-free decomposition does not rely on the fact that the system size is three, we can increase the system size by adding further interactions

such as

$$H_{\text{Ising}} = \sum_{i \in \{1,4,\dots,1+3m\}} (Z_i Z_{i+1} + Z_i Z_{i+2} + Z_{i+1} Z_{i+2})$$

Here H_{Ising} is a $3(1+m)$ qubit Hamiltonian with $m \in \mathbb{Z}^>$ and has ground energy $E_0 = -m$. Consider a three-local decomposition, $H_{\text{Ising}} = \sum_i H_i$, where $H_i = Z_i Z_{i+1} + Z_i Z_{i+2} + Z_{i+1} Z_{i+2}$. Each H_i has ground energy $E_0^i = -1$. Since there are m such three-local terms, we see that the ground state for H_{Ising} simultaneously minimises the energy of each H_i . Hence, we see that this decomposition of H_{Ising} constitutes a three-local, frustration-free decomposition. As a result, the Hamiltonian

$$H = X_1 \otimes \left[-mI - \sum_{i \in \{1,4,\dots,1+3m\}} (Z_i Z_{i+1} + Z_i Z_{i+2} + Z_{i+1} Z_{i+2}) \right]$$

admits a four-local unrestricted decomposition and is thus four-locally stoquastic.

Ising model on triangular lattice

Building on this, we can now consider $G = (V, E)$ being the triangular lattice and $H_{\text{lattice}} = \sum_{(u,v) \in E} Z_u Z_v$. We will illustrate the reasoning through the example of the rhombus-shaped triangular lattice, however, the same argument applies to the triangle-shaped triangular lattice. The rhombus-shaped triangular lattice is a planar graph where the unbounded face borders with an even number of edges while all internal faces border with an odd number of edges. We know [5] that for this type of Hamiltonian, faces containing an odd number of $+1$ weighted edges, are frustrated while those with an even number of $+1$ weighted edges are not. Hence the ground state is highly degenerate and corresponds to every internal face having a single unsatisfied edge. We can two-colour the internal faces of the lattice so that no two faces of the same colour share an edge as in figure 2.2. The ground energy of the Hamiltonian is $E_0 = -M + 2K$ where M is the number of edges and K is the number of internal faces of colour A , which is exactly half the total number of internal faces.

Figure 2.2: Representation of a ground state for H_{lattice} on 6×6 rhombus-shaped triangular lattice with two colouring of internal faces. Unsatisfied edges are coloured red.

To see that H_{lattice} admits a three-local frustration-free decomposition, consider

$$H_{\text{lattice}} = \sum_{ijk} H_{ijk} + B,$$

where $H_{ijk} = Z_i Z_j + Z_j Z_k + Z_i Z_k$ and the sum goes over all triples of vertices (i, j, k) defining faces of colour A . Every edge borders a face of colour A except of half the edges bordering the unbounded face. In order to recover the correct Hamiltonian from the decomposition, $B = \sum_{(j,k) \in E'} (+Z_j Z_k)$ where E' is the set of edges, bordering the unbounded face, not contained in the faces of colour A . For an $L \times W$ lattice, the number of internal faces is $2(L-1)(W-1)$ and the total number of edges is $3(L-1)(W-1) + (L-1) + (W-1)$, hence $E_0 = -(L-1)(W-1) - (L-1) - (W-1)$. The number of terms H_{ijk} is exactly $(L-1)(W-1)$ and the number of terms in B is $(L-1) + (W-1)$. Each term H_{ijk} corresponds to a frustrated triangle and has minimum energy -1 . Since each 2-local term in B is of the form $Z_i Z_j$ it also has minimum energy -1 . We can, non-uniquely, assign the two-local terms in B to the three-local groupings H_{ijk} . Hence we see that $H = \sum_{ijk} H'_{ijk}$ is three-local frustration-free as the ground state of H simultaneously minimises all H'_{ijk} terms.

Frustrated Ising rings and planar graphs

Moving to more general constructions we can consider the 1-D Ising Hamiltonian with periodic boundary conditions

$$H_{\text{ring}} = \sum_{i=2}^N J_{i,i+1} Z_i Z_{i+1} + J_{2,N+1} Z_2 Z_{N+1},$$

with $J_{i,j} \in \{+1, -1\}$ and an odd number of coefficients $J_{i,j} = +1$. Due to the last condition this closed chain is frustrated [5] with ground energy $E_0 = -N + 1 = -M + 2$ where M is the number of edges in the chain. We will see that this type of Hamiltonian also admits a three-local frustration-free decomposition.

Lemma 0.2. *Given a frustrated Ising ring*

$$H_{\text{ring}} = \sum_{i=2}^N J_{i,i+1} Z_i Z_{i+1} + J_{2,N+1} Z_2 Z_{N+1},$$

with $J_{i,j} \in \{+1, -1\}$ and an odd number of coefficients $J_{i,j} = +1$. We can construct two closed, frustrated chains by connecting an arbitrary vertex u to another, non-neighbouring vertex v by a double edge one of which has weight $J_{uv}^+ = +1$ and the other having weight $J_{uv}^- = -1$. The two chains are given by

$$H_1 = \sum_{i=u}^v J_{i,i+1} Z_i Z_{i+1} + J_{u,v}^{+/-} Z_u Z_v$$

$$H_2 = H_{\text{ring}} - \sum_{i=u}^v J_{i,i+1} Z_i Z_{i+1} + J_{u,v}^{-/+} Z_u Z_v$$

Figure 2.3: Left hand side: Frustrated Ising ring. Right hand side: Triangulation step via addition of fictitious interactions. We have coloured edges with weight $+1$ (red) and -1 (black). Blue, triangular faces correspond to three-local groupings.

Proof. For an Ising ring to be frustrated we need to have an odd number of edges with weight $J_{i,j} = +1$. The bipartition of the bounded face, established via connecting two non-neighbouring vertices (u, v) gives rise to one set of edges with an odd number of $+1$ weights and one set of edges with an even number of $+1$ weights (as the total is odd). Assigning J_{uv}^- to the set with an odd number of $+1$ weighted edges and J_{uv}^+ to the set with an even number of $+1$ weighted edges, results in two sets with an odd number of $+1$ weighted edges. These correspond to H_1 and H_2 which are both frustrated. \square

Hence we have shown that for a frustrated Ising Hamiltonian on a ring, $H_{\text{ring}} = H_1 + H_2$ where H_1 and H_2 are both frustrated rings. Using such fictitious couplings between a vertex u and all non-neighbouring vertices, we can break a frustrated chain of length M into $M - 2$ frustrated chains of length three, see figure 2.3. The minimum energy of every such frustrated triangle is -1 and so we can decompose

$$H_{\text{ring}} = \sum_{v,w} H_{uvw},$$

where each $H_{uvw} = J_{uv}Z_uZ_v + J_{uw}Z_uZ_w + J_{vw}Z_vZ_w$ corresponds to a frustrated triangle, i.e $J_{uv} \times J_{uw} \times J_{vw} = +1$ for all triples (u, v, w) . Since there are $M - 2$ terms H_{uvw} and the ground energy of the total Hamiltonian is $E_0 = -M + 2$, we see that the ground state for H minimises all H_{uvw} . Thus, the decomposition is frustration-free. For example let's consider

$$\begin{aligned} H_{\text{ring}} = & -Z_2Z_3 + Z_3Z_4 - Z_4Z_5 + Z_5Z_6 + Z_6Z_7 \\ & - Z_7Z_8 - Z_8Z_9 - Z_2Z_9, \end{aligned}$$

represented graphically in figure 2.3. Clearly this Hamiltonian does not admit any two-local frustration-free decomposition, as it has an odd number of $+1$ edges. However, we can perform the triangulation described, to show that the following three-local decomposition is indeed frustration-free.

$$H_{\text{ring}} = \sum_{i=3}^8 H_{2,i,i+1}; \quad H_{234} = -Z_2Z_3 - Z_2Z_4 + Z_3Z_4, \quad H_{245} = Z_2Z_4 - Z_4Z_5 - Z_2Z_4,$$

$$H_{256} = Z_2Z_5 + Z_5Z_6 + Z_2Z_6, \quad H_{267} = -Z_2Z_6 + Z_6Z_7 - Z_2Z_7,$$

$$H_{278} = Z_2Z_7 - Z_7Z_8 + Z_2Z_8, \quad H_{289} = Z_2Z_8 - Z_2Z_9 - Z_2Z_9$$

Since each term has an odd number of $J_{ij} = +1$, all of them are frustrated with minimum energy -1 . Thus, the sum of local ground energies is equal to the total ground energy E_0 .

We can use the above method of triangulating frustrated faces, in order to show that a broad family of Ising Hamiltonians admits three-local frustration-free decompositions. In order to define this family of Ising Hamiltonians let us introduce the following procedure. Given a planar graph $G = (V, E)$ and Ising Hamiltonian $H = \sum_{(i,j) \in E} J_{ij} Z_i Z_j$ with $J_{ij} \in \{-1, 0, +1\}$:

1. Construct the graph $G_0 = (V, E_0)$ corresponding to a ground state of H as defined at the beginning of this section.
2. For every unsatisfied edge U in G_i , assign the pair (C, U) where C is an atomic cycle such that $U \in C$ and no other unsatisfied edge $V \in C$. If no such pairing exists move to step 4.
3. Construct the graph $G_{i+1} := (V, E_i \setminus E_c)$ where $E_c = \{e \in C\}$ and move to step 2.
4. If G_i does not contain any unsatisfied edges output YES and halt. If G_i does contain at least one unsatisfied edge, restart the whole procedure using a different assignment of pairs than in the previous n runs calling this the $n := n + 1$ run. If no other assignment exists output NO and halt.

An example of how this procedure works is depicted in figure 2.4.

Definition 10. *We will say that a Hamiltonian $H_{\text{Ising}} = \sum_{(i,j) \in E} J_{ij} Z_i Z_j$ with $J_{ij} \in \{-1, 0, 1\}$ on a planar graph $G = (V, E)$ belongs to the class $\{H_s\}$, when there exists a ground state of H such that, the above defined procedure outputs YES.*

By definition, for any $H_{\text{Ising}} \in \{H_s\}$, each C contains one unsatisfied edge, therefore the ground energy of H_{Ising} is $\sum_i (-m_i + 2) - K$ where m_i is the length of the i^{th} atomic cycle C and K is the number of left-over edges after all cycles have been removed. Each cycle C contains a single unsatisfied edge and therefore corresponds to a frustrated face. We can therefore use the same triangulation method as for the Ising ring. For each such

Figure 2.4: Top: Graph representing part of the ground state of some H with unsatisfied edges in red. The blue shaded faces are bordered by edges corresponding to atomic cycles C . Middle: After one iteration of the procedure the edges corresponding to C_1 are removed. Bottom: After four iterations all edges belonging to atomic cycles C_1, C_2, C_3, C_4 are removed and no unsatisfied edge remains.

cycle we can take the decomposition $\sum_{(u,v) \in C} J_{uv} Z_u Z_v = \sum_{uvw} H_{uvw}$ where the sum goes over all triples defining a frustrated triangle. The K remaining edges after removal of each cycle can, non-uniquely, be grouped into three-local terms. These edges will either belong to open chains or to unfrustrated faces. Therefore every such grouping will have the same minimum energy configuration with energy $-K$. Hence the sum of the ground energies of all three-local terms H_{uvw} is $\sum_i (-m_i + 2) - K$.

Figure 2.5: Representation of ground state of Ising Hamiltonian on maximal planar graph with 5 vertices. Every face is frustrated as it borders with three edges all with $+1$ weight. Red edges are unsatisfied.

Finally, let's consider $G = (V, E)$ a maximal planar graph, i.e a graph which becomes non-planar by the addition of any further edge, and $H_m = \sum_{(i,j) \in E} Z_i Z_j$ on n qubits. Maximal planar graphs have the property that all the faces in the graph have three boundary edges and since the weights of all interactions of H_m are positive, all faces are frustrated, as can be seen in the example in figure 2.5. Maximal planar graphs have $3n - 6$ edges and $2n - 4$ faces, where n is the number of vertices. Since all faces are triangular and frustrated, any ground state configuration will have a single unsatisfied edge bordering each face. It follows that the ground energy is $E_0 = -(3n - 6) + (2n - 4) = -n + 2$. We can consider the following three-local decomposition

$$H_m = \sum_{(i,j,k) \in F} \frac{1}{2} (Z_i Z_j + Z_i Z_k + Z_j Z_k),$$

where F is the set of all faces. Since each edge is shared between two faces, the decomposition recovers the correct global Hamiltonian. Furthermore, since every term $\frac{1}{2}(Z_i Z_j + Z_i Z_k + Z_j Z_k)$ is frustrated, it has minimum energy $-1/2$. As the number of faces is $2n - 4$, there are that many terms in the decomposition, therefore the sum of the ground energies of the local terms is equal to the ground energy of the global Hamiltonian. Thus, the three-local decomposition considered is indeed frustration-free.

We have seen a number of Hamiltonians H_{Ising} which admit three-local frustration-free decompositions while not admitting any two-local frustration-free decompositions. As a result, the respective Hamiltonians $H = X_1 \otimes (E_0 - H_{\text{Ising}})$ are not locally stoquastic when a three-local decomposition is considered, but are locally stoquastic when we consider a four-local decomposition. Building on this, one can consider more elaborate approaches, combining the triangulation step introduced, as well as distributing two-local terms $J_{i,j} Z_i Z_j$ over a number of three-local groupings (as was done in the last example). It is conceivable that such strategies will allow us to find larger classes of Hamiltonians for which three-local frustration-free decompositions exist, while all two-local decompositions are frustrated. However, there is no reason to believe that this should always be possible and one can indeed show, modulo one complexity theoretic assumption, that there exist Hamiltonians of the type $H = X_1 \otimes (E_0 - H_{\text{Ising}})$ for which this is not the case, see Proposition 10.

2.3 Summary

In this chapter we have introduced the notions of global and local stoquasticity showing when they coincide and when they don't, as well as providing some basic properties of stoquastic Hamiltonians in general. In the next chapter we will introduce the basic ideas concerning complexity theory and apply them to study some problems with respect to global/local stoquastic Hamiltonians.

Chapter 3

Complexity theory

Given a mathematical problem, it is often of interest to know whether there can, in principle, exist an algorithm which solves all its instances and if this is the case, what the run-time of such an algorithm is. Computability and complexity theory is the formal framework within which one seeks to answer such questions. Crucially, the framework is flexible enough so that statements about physically relevant problems can be made, and as such it is a widely applicable tool. For example, it was recently shown by Cubitt, Perez-Garcia and Wolf that there does not exist a general algorithm for deciding whether a given Hamiltonian has a spectral gap [13] i.e it is an undecidable problem. However, knowing that there exists an algorithm for a certain problem does not tell us, a priori, anything about its efficiency. In that regard, a plethora of physically relevant problems have been identified to not be, modulo assumptions, efficiently solvable. Perhaps the most important representative of this class of problems is the ground energy problem of a given Hamiltonian, both in the classical and the quantum regime. We will introduce some of the basic principles regarding complexity theory before analysing the complexity of the ground energy problem for stoquastic Hamiltonians.

3.1 Computing functions

To be able to make any precise statements about the required effort of solving a given problem, it is necessary to establish some common ground regarding the very notion of computation. To this end we introduce the idea of computable functions, which can be understood as functions $f(x)$ for which there exists an algorithm-i.e a set of rules taking x as input and giving $f(x)$ as output-for all x in their domain. Importantly, the definition of a computable function makes no statement about the *efficiency* with which the algorithm produces $f(x)$, but merely that it has to do so in a finite number of steps. As mentioned in the introduction there exist problems which are in fact undecidable i.e they correspond to functions which are not computable. This understanding was pioneered independently by Gödel and Turing. [43].

Computable functions can be defined in a constructive manner with respect to different

models of computation, such as Turing machines, the circuit model or λ calculus. A model of computation is a formal description of what we commonly understand as an algorithm. It is not necessary to analyse every problem with respect to all computational models, as it has been shown that Turing machines are equivalent models to all known physical models of computation [4]. There exist various ways to define Turing machines which are, again, all computationally equivalent to each other [39]. Here we will introduce the k -tape version which, informally, is a mechanical apparatus consisting of k infinite tapes of cells holding symbols σ . The first tape, known as the input tape, is equipped with a read-only head while the remaining $k - 1$ tapes have a read-write head. The k^{th} tape is known as the output tape which holds the result of the computation after the machine has come to a halt. In addition the machine is equipped with a register that holds the internal state, Q , which determines the machine's action in the next step. The series of steps it follows is given by some transition function devised in such a way, as for the machine to correctly compute the given function. At every time step the k heads read the content of the cell they are placed over and the $k - 1$ read-write heads update the entry of their cells according to the transition function. Furthermore, the state of the machine is updated and finally, the heads are allowed to either stay on the same cell or move one cell to the left/right. The machine continues this process until the state is updated to the halting state, q_H , whereupon the entry in the output tape is taken as the result of the computation [4].

3.2 Complexity classes and reductions

We are interested in classifying computable functions according to how resources, needed for their computation, scale with the problem size. The resource we will be considering is time, i.e the number of steps needed for a Turing Machine to perform the computation. One could also consider other resources such as space, i.e the number of cells used in the computation by the Turing Machine. The input size can be formally seen as the number of tape cells required to describe the problem.

Definition 11 (Language/Decision problem [4]). *A decision problem asks whether the answer to a given problem, represented by a Boolean function $f(x)$, upon input $x \in \{0, 1\}^*$ is YES ($f(x) = 1$) or NO ($f(x) = 0$). The language $L_f \subseteq \{0, 1\}^*$, corresponding to the decision problem represented by $f(x)$, is the set $L_f = \{x : f(x) = 1\}$. For a language $L \subseteq \{0, 1\}^*$, the complement of L is denoted by $\bar{L} = \{0, 1\}^* \setminus L$.*

A language L_f specifies the decision problem represented by $f(x)$ by listing all its YES instances. There also exists a generalisation of decision problems known as promise problems, for which the input is promised to be a subset of all possible inputs.

Definition 12 (Promise problem[39]). *A promise problem is defined via a pair of sets $L_{YES}, L_{NO} \subseteq \{0, 1\}^*$, such that $L_{YES} \cap L_{NO} = \emptyset$. The set of possible inputs $L_{YES} \cup L_{NO} \subseteq \{0, 1\}^*$ is called the promise. A promise problem asks whether the answer to a given problem, represented by a Boolean function $f(x)$, upon input $x \in L_{YES} \cup L_{NO}$, is YES ($f(x) = 1 \implies x \in L_{YES}$) or NO ($f(x) = 0 \implies x \in L_{NO}$).*

Clearly if $L_{\text{YES}} \cup L_{\text{NO}} = \{0, 1\}^*$ the above definition reduces to that of a regular decision problem.

We can group the complexity classes discussed here depending whether they are concerned with finding the solution to a problem or verifying it, as well as whether deterministic, probabilistic or quantum computations are considered. This is summarised in the following table.

	Decidable Problems	Verifiable Problems
Deterministic comp.	P	NP
Probabilistic comp.	BPP	AM, MA, StoqMA
Quantum comp.	BQP	QMA

3.2.1 Deterministic computations

Here we define complexity classes which either entail problems which can be decided or verified in polynomial-time using a Turing machine.

Definition 13 (Complexity class **P** [39]). **P** is defined as the set of decision problems decidable in polynomial-time.

Definition 14 (Complexity class **NP** [4]). A language $L \subseteq \{0, 1\}^*$ is in **NP** if there exists a polynomial $p : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ and a polynomial-time Turing machine M such that:

$$\begin{aligned} \forall x \in L, \exists w \in \{0, 1\}^{p(|x|)} : M(x, w) = 1 & \quad (\text{completeness}) \\ \forall x \notin L, \forall w \in \{0, 1\}^{p(|x|)} : M(x, w) \neq 1 & \quad (\text{soundness}) \end{aligned}$$

Here w is called a polynomial witness for x .

A polynomial-time Turing machine is a Turing machine which will halt after a polynomial number (in the input size) of steps. Problems in **NP** therefore admit a perfectly sound and complete polynomial-time witness i.e all YES instances are accepted with certainty, while NO instances are always rejected. Alternatively the complexity class **NP** can be understood as an interaction between an all-powerful agent called Merlin (the prover) and Arthur (the verifier) who is only in possession of a Turing machine. A problem L is in **NP** if for all instances $x \in L$, Merlin can provide a proof to Arthur which he can verify efficiently, while for all instances $x \notin L$ there does not exist a prove that could trick Arthur into accepting it. As we will see, there exist more complexity classes which can be defined with respect to such Arthur-Merlin games, by varying the computational power of Arthur, as well as the way they interact.

Definition 15 (Complexity class **coNP** [4]). A language $L \subseteq \{0, 1\}^*$ is in **coNP** if the complement language $\bar{L} \in \text{NP}$

3.2.2 Probabilistic computations

In addition to the above defined *deterministic* Turing machine, there also exists a notion of so-called *probabilistic* Turing machines [4]. Instead of having a single transition function which entails the steps needed for the computation, we now have two transition functions. At every time step in the computation the Turing machine chooses with equal probability between one of the two functions. In addition to the special halting state, there is also a state q_{accept} and we say that the Turing machine outputs 1 when it has reached that state while outputting 0 when it halts without reaching q_{accept} . We say that a probabilistic Turing machine has decided the problem if it outputs the right answer with probability at least $2/3$. That is to say it outputs 1 if the answer to the problem is YES and 0 if it is NO.

Definition 16 (Complexity class **BPP** [4]). *A language $L \subseteq \{0, 1\}^*$ is in **BPP** if there exists a polynomial-time probabilistic Turing machine such that*

$$\begin{aligned} \forall x \in L, \mathbb{P}(M(x) = 1) &\geq \frac{2}{3} \text{ (completeness)} \\ \forall x \notin L, \mathbb{P}(M(x) = 1) &\leq \frac{1}{3} \text{ (soundness)} \end{aligned}$$

The complexity class **BPP** is the probabilistic analogue to **P** and although we will not make much use of it in the thesis we present it for completeness.

Definition 17 (Complexity class promise-**AM** [10]). *A promise problem defined via $L_{\text{YES}} \cup L_{\text{NO}} \subseteq \{0, 1\}^*$ is in **AM** iff there exists a polynomial $p(n)$ and polynomial-time Turing machine $M(x, w, q)$ defined for any $q, w \in \{0, 1\}^{p(|x|)}$ such that*

$$\begin{aligned} \forall x \in L_{\text{YES}}, \mathbb{P}(\exists w : M(x, w, q) = 1) &\geq \frac{2}{3} \text{ (completeness)} \\ \forall x \in L_{\text{NO}}, \mathbb{P}(\exists w : M(x, w, q) = 1) &\leq \frac{1}{3} \text{ (soundness)} \end{aligned}$$

Here q is a uniformly distributed random bit string chosen by Arthur, w is the witness given by Merlin as a response and x is an instance of the problem. If $x \notin L_{\text{YES}} \cup L_{\text{NO}}$, $M(x, w, q)$ is arbitrary or undefined.

We will simply refer to promise-**AM** as **AM** from here onwards.

Definition 18 (Complexity class promise-**MA** [10]). *A promise problem defined via $L_{\text{YES}} \cup L_{\text{NO}} \subseteq \{0, 1\}^*$ is in **MA** if there exists a polynomial $p(n)$ and a polynomial-time probabilistic Turing machine $M(x, w)$, taking as input bitstrings $x \in \{0, 1\}^*$, $w \in \{0, 1\}^{p(|x|)}$ such that*

$$\begin{aligned} \forall x \in L_{\text{YES}} \exists w : \mathbb{P}(M(x, w) = 1) &\geq \frac{2}{3} \text{ (completeness)} \\ \forall x \notin L_{\text{NO}} \forall w : \mathbb{P}(M(x, w) = 1) &\leq \frac{1}{3} \text{ (soundness)} \end{aligned}$$

Here w is the polynomial-time witness provided by Merlin and x is an instance of the problem. If $x \notin L_{\text{YES}} \cup L_{\text{NO}}$, $M(x, w)$ is arbitrary or undefined.

As with **AM** we will simply refer to promise-**MA** as **MA**. The classes **AM** and **MA** appear frequently in the study of stoquastic Hamiltonians as we will see in section 3.3. There is another class which was defined by Bravyi, Bessen and Terhal in [8] for studying stoquastic Hamiltonians, called **StoqMA**, sitting right between **AM** and **MA**. In a way **AM** and **MA** can be understood as probabilistic analogues to the class **NP** with the main difference between **AM** and **MA** being that in the former Arthur challenges Merlin while in the later Merlin provides the witness straight away [10].

3.2.3 Quantum computations

It is possible to extend this further and define what is known as a quantum Turing machine, however, it is more convenient, and in fact equivalent, to use *polynomial-time uniform families of quantum circuits* instead [47]. A quantum circuit takes as input a quantum state $|x\rangle$ of n qubits, where $x \in \{0, 1\}^n$. It is allowed to then perform operations from a *universal gate set* (see [47]) and finally measure in the computational basis. As the size of the input string x can vary, we need to consider a family of quantum circuits $\{Q_n : n \in \mathbb{N}\}$ for which there exists a Turing machine which on input n constructs, in polynomial-time, a description of the circuit. Such families of quantum circuits are called polynomial-time generated.

Definition 19 (Complexity class **BQP** [47]). *A language $L \subseteq \{0, 1\}^*$ is in **BQP** if there exists a family of polynomial-time generated, uniform quantum circuits $\{Q_n : n \in \mathbb{N}\}$, such that each circuit Q_n takes n qubits as input, producing one output qubit.*

$$\begin{aligned} \forall x \in L, \mathbb{P}(Q(x) = 1) &\geq \frac{2}{3} \text{ (completeness)} \\ \forall x \notin L, \mathbb{P}(Q(x) = 1) &\leq \frac{1}{3} \text{ (soundness)} \end{aligned}$$

where $Q(x)$ is the measurement outcome, 0 or 1, of the output qubit in the computational basis.

Definition 20 (Complexity class **QMA** [47]). *A language $L \subseteq \{0, 1\}^*$ is in **QMA** iff there exists a family of polynomial-time uniform quantum circuits $\{Q_n : n \in \mathbb{N}\}$, such that:*

$$\begin{aligned} \forall x \in L \exists |\psi\rangle : \mathbb{P}(Q(|x\rangle |\psi\rangle) = 1) &\geq \frac{2}{3} \text{ (completeness)} \\ \forall x \notin L \forall |\psi\rangle : \mathbb{P}(Q(|x\rangle |\psi\rangle) = 1) &\leq \frac{1}{3} \text{ (soundness)} \end{aligned}$$

where $|\psi\rangle$ is a poly(n) witness state and $Q(|x\rangle |\psi\rangle)$ is the measurement outcome 0 or 1 of the output qubit measured in the computational basis.

We can see **BQP** and **QMA** as the quantum analogues of **BPP** and **MA** or **P** and **NP**. As such, problems in **BQP** can be decided correctly and with high probability in

polynomial time using a quantum computer, while **QMA** entails those problems which can be verified efficiently and with high probability using such a device.

The following diagram illustrates the known relations between the previously discussed complexity classes.

Figure 3.1: Known relations between complexity classes. If class **A** is connected to **B** and lies above it, we have $B \subseteq A$, e.g. $P \subseteq NP$.

Having defined a few of the relevant complexity classes and given relations between them, we now turn our attention to the study of individual problems rather than entire complexity classes. One powerful tool in the study of any computational problem are so-called reductions. These allow us to infer something about the complexity of the problem at hand, using the complexity of some other problem.

3.2.4 Karp reductions and complete problems

Polynomial time or Karp reduction is a way to relate different computational problems, using a hypothetical algorithm for one as a subroutine for the other. Problem **A** is said to be Karp reducible to problem **B**, if there exists a polynomial-time algorithm for **A** calling solutions to **B** polynomially many times. If **A** is reducible to **B** in this way, it is clear that **B** is at least as hard as **A**. If there exists an algorithm for **B** we can thus infer an algorithm for **A** with only polynomial overhead. Furthermore, if one can prove that there does not exist a polynomial algorithm for **A**, there can also not exist one for **B**.

Definition 21 (Karp reduction [4]). *A language $A \subseteq \{0, 1\}^*$ is Karp reducible to a language $B \subseteq \{0, 1\}^*$, $A \leq_K B$ if there exists polynomial-time computable function $f : \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \{0, 1\}^*$ such that for all $x \in \{0, 1\}^*$, $x \in A$ iff $f(x) \in B$. Here f corresponds to a polynomial-time algorithm for A calling solutions to B .*

One of the most remarkable results emerging from the use of reductions is the existence of complete problems for various complexity classes. If $A \leq_K B$ for every problem A in complexity class \mathbf{C} , B is said to be a hard problem for \mathbf{C} . If furthermore, $B \in \mathbf{C}$ it is a complete problem for \mathbf{C} . If some problem A can be shown to be a hard problem for \mathbf{C} and A is reducible to some other problem A' , it follows that A' is also a hard problem for \mathbf{C} . The importance of this stems from the fact that once we have found a problem which we can prove to be hard for a certain complexity class, we can always try to reduce that to any given problem. Repeated application of this provides us with an ever growing number of problems we can use for further reductions. Of particular interest are problems which are complete for the class \mathbf{NP} since, modulo the believe that $\mathbf{NP} \neq \mathbf{P}$, such problems do not admit any polynomial-time algorithm. The first complete problem shown to be \mathbf{NP} -complete is \mathbf{SAT} and the reduction, is known as the Cook-Levin theorem [39]. Similarly in the context of quantum computations, problems which are complete for \mathbf{QMA} are believed to not admit a polynomial-time algorithm using a quantum Turing machine (equivalently, polynomial-time generated, uniform family of quantum circuits). In this thesis we will use Karp reductions to show that the problem of finding local unitary rotations under which a Hamiltonian is stoquastic, is \mathbf{NP} -complete (for two-local Hamiltonians with 1-local terms) by reducing 3-SAT to it [26]. Furthermore, we will show that the problem of deciding whether a Hamiltonian is globally-stoquastic in a fixed basis is \mathbf{coNP} -complete for 3-local Hamiltonians, by reducing a spin glass problem (Theorem 2) to it.

Definition 22 (Boolean formulae [4]). *A Boolean formula ϕ over variables u_1, \dots, u_n each taking the value "True" $\rightarrow 1$ or "False" $\rightarrow 0$ is an expression consisting of these variables linked via logical operators "AND"(\wedge), "NOT"(\neg) and "OR"(\vee). We say that ϕ is satisfiable if $\exists z \in \{0, 1\}^n$ such that $\phi(z) = 1$ while ϕ is unsatisfiable if $\forall z \in \{0, 1\}^n$ we have $\phi(z) = 0$.*

Any Boolean formula can be converted to an equivalent formula in conjunctive normal form (CNF), meaning it is an AND of OR's of variables or their negations

$$\bigwedge_i \left(\bigvee_j v_{i_j} \right)$$

where v_{i_j} are the literals of the formula and $v_{i_j} = u_k$ or $v_{i_j} = \neg u_k$. Each of i terms $\bigvee_j v_{i_j}$ is called a clause.

Definition 23 (SAT). *Define SAT as the language of all satisfiable CNF formulae.*

Definition 24 (k-SAT). *Define k-SAT as the language of all satisfiable kCNF formulae where each clause contains at most k literals.*

Theorem 1 (Cook-Levin theorem). *SAT is NP-complete [39]*

It is straightforward to see that SAT is in NP as the very assignment which satisfies the Boolean formula can be used as an efficiently verifiable witness.

Proposition 8. *SAT \leq_p 3-SAT and therefore 3-SAT is NP-complete [4]*

The reduction of SAT to 3-SAT will be achieved by showing that there exists an encoding for every k -CNF formula ϕ , with $k > 3$ into a 3-CNF formula ψ . Since finding a satisfying assignment for k -CNF is NP-complete, see Theorem 1, so is the problem of finding a satisfying assignment for 3-CNF, which completes the reduction. To see that such an encoding always exists consider a 4-CNF clause $u_1 \vee u_2 \vee \bar{u}_3 \vee u_4$. We can split this clause into two $(u_1 \vee u_2 \vee \bar{z}) \wedge (\bar{u}_3 \vee u_4 \vee z)$ where z is a new variable. As we can see, if there exists a satisfying assignment of 4-CNF, there exists z such that both 3-CNF are satisfied. If there is no satisfying assignment for 4-CNF, there is none for 3-CNF either.

3.3 Local Hamiltonian problem and stoquasticity

A particularly important problem from the perspective of physicists, chemists and materials scientists, is that of estimating the ground energy of a given Hamiltonian. Restricting first to classical Hamiltonians which are diagonal in the computational basis, it was shown by Barahona that this problem is already intractable.

Theorem 2 (PS [6]). *Given a planar graph $G = (V, E)$ and an integer K . Deciding whether there exists a configuration of $S_i \in \{+1, -1\}$ such that*

$$\sum_{(i,j) \in E} S_i S_j + \sum_i S_i \leq K$$

is an NP-complete problem which we call planar spin glass (PS).

Considering general, quantum Hamiltonians, it was shown by Kitaev that the problem of estimating their ground energy, is a complete problem for QMA. This can be seen as an analogue result to the Cook/Levin theorem [3]. More formally we define the local Hamiltonian problem.

Definition 25 (k-LocalHamiltonian problem (LH) [23]). *Given is a k -local Hamiltonian on n qubits $H = \sum_{i=1}^m H_i$ where $m = \text{poly}(n)$ and $\|H_i\| \leq \text{poly}(n)$ and H_i is specified by $\text{poly}(n)$ bits. Decide, given the promise that either of the two is true*

1. YES: The ground energy of H , $\lambda(H) \leq \alpha$
2. NO: The ground energy of H , $\lambda(H) > \gamma$

Where α, γ are rational numbers specified by $\text{poly}(n)$ bits such that $\gamma - \alpha \geq 1/\text{poly}(n)$

Theorem 3. *The 5-LocalHamiltonian problem is QMA-complete [25].*

The locality for which the local Hamiltonian problem is QMA-complete, was then reduced to three by Kempe and Regev [24]. Subsequently Kempe, Kitaev and Regev also showed that the problem is still QMA-complete when two-local Hamiltonians are considered. For this they introduced a novel technique based on perturbation theory. This technique works by introducing a Hamiltonian $H_{\text{parent}} = \Delta H_0 + H_{\text{pert.}}$ where Δ is a large constant so that the first term dominates the Hamiltonian. The ground space of H_{parent} is thus given by the perturbatively modified ground space of H_0 , induced by the perturbation term $H_{\text{pert.}}$ which gives rise to an effective Hamiltonian. Choosing H_{parent} to be two-local, it is possible to get an effective Hamiltonian which is k -local. In fact this technique was applied by Oliveira and Terhal to show that the two-local Hamiltonian problem is QMA-complete, even when restricted to nearest neighbour interactions on a 2-D lattice [36]. Since then it has seen application in many more occasions, e.g in showing that certain *universal* Hamiltonians can approximately simulate, in their low energy subspace, entire families of Hamiltonians [12].

3.3.1 Stoquastic local Hamiltonian problem

Having introduced the general k -LocalHamiltonian problem and having seen that it is a complete problem for QMA, it follows naturally to consider the equivalent problem under the constraint that the Hamiltonian is stoquastic. Since the defining characteristic of stoquastic Hamiltonians is that they are sign problem free and therefore amenable to Monte Carlo simulations, we would like to see whether they are distinct from generic quantum Hamiltonians using a complexity theoretic approach. As we have seen in the first chapter, there are two notions of stoquasticity one can refer to. Thus we introduce the following two problems, the first of which was first considered by Bravyi, DiVincenzo, Oliveira and Terhal.

Definition 26 (Locally-stoquastic, local Hamiltonian problem (Local-Stoq-LH)[9]). *k -local Hamiltonian problem with the restriction that $H = \sum_i H_i$ where each k -local term H_i is a symmetric Z -matrix in the computational basis.*

Definition 27 (Globally-stoquastic, local Hamiltonian problem (Global-Stoq-LH)). *k -local Hamiltonian problem with the restriction that H is a symmetric Z -matrix in the computational basis.*

Clearly, every classical Hamiltonian is stoquastic as it has vanishing off-diagonal matrix elements. From Theorem 2 it follows that Global/Local-Stoq-LH is at least NP-hard [7]. In [9] it was shown that Local-Stoq-LH is in fact in AM and is a complete problem for MA if $k \geq 6$.

Theorem 4 (Local-Stoq-LH \in AM). *k -local, locally-stoquastic Hamiltonian problem \in AM [9].*

Since we will use the proof as presented in [9] to show that also $\text{Global-Stoq-LH} \in \mathbf{AM}$, as well as generally $\text{LH} \in \mathbf{AM}$ for sign problem free Hamiltonians (see Definition 30) it will be useful to sketch it out. For technical details one should advice the original paper [9].

Consider the positive semidefinite matrix

$$G = 1/2(I - H/C),$$

where $C = \sum_i \|H_i\|$ and hence $0 \leq \langle x|G|y \rangle \leq 1 \forall x, y \in \{0, 1\}^n$. As G is related to H via a shift and a sign inversion, we can see that the local Hamiltonian problem for H , Definition 25, is equivalent to asking whether the largest eigenvalue of G , $\mu(G)$, satisfies $\mu(G) \geq \mu_+$ or $\mu(G) \leq \mu_-$. Due to the invariance of the trace under basis transformations, it is clear that $\text{Tr}(G^L) \geq \mu(G)^L$ if L is an even integer. We have

$$\begin{aligned} \mu(G) \geq \mu_+ &\implies \text{Tr}(G^L) \geq \mu_+^L \\ \mu(G) \leq \mu_- &\implies \text{Tr}(G^L) \leq 2^n \mu_-^L \end{aligned}$$

In the proposed procedure, Merlin therefore tries to prove that $\text{Tr}(G^L) \geq \mu_+^L$ for YES instances. In the special case where the thresholds α, γ of the local Hamiltonian problem are $\alpha = 0, \gamma = 1/m$ (where $m = \text{poly}(n)$) we can define the respective thresholds $\mu_+ = 1/2, \mu_- = (1/2)(1 - 1/Cm)$.

One then proceeds by expressing the evaluation of $\text{Tr}(G^L)$ as the problem of estimating the size of a set Ω , which can be shown to be a problem in \mathbf{AM} . Since $\langle x|G|y \rangle$ is a real number between 0 and 1, expressible as a binary string of length m , Lemma 1 from the original paper is invoked, to establish that each matrix element can be expressed as the expected value of a Boolean function $f(x, y; t)$ under uniformly distributed strings t

$$\langle x|G|y \rangle = \frac{1}{2^m} \sum_{t \in \Sigma^m} f(x, y; t).$$

Replacing the Boolean function $f(x, y; t)$ by the binary matrix $G(t)$, such that $\langle x|G(t)|y \rangle$ corresponds to $f(x, y; t)$, we can express

$$G = \frac{1}{2^m} \sum_{t \in \Sigma^m} G(t)$$

Expressing $\text{Tr}(G^L)$ in the computational basis and inserting identity operators between each G we get

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Tr}(G^L) &= \sum_{\{x\}} \langle x_1|G|x_2 \rangle \langle x_2| \dots \langle x_L|G|x_1 \rangle \\ &= \frac{1}{2^{mL}} \sum_{\{x\}} \sum_{\{t\}} \langle x_1|G(t_1)|x_2 \rangle \langle x_2| \dots \langle x_L|G(t_L)|x_1 \rangle. \end{aligned}$$

Since $G(t_i)$ are binary matrices, $F(s) = \langle x_1 | G(t_1) | x_2 \rangle \langle x_2 | \dots \langle x_L | G(t_L) | x_1 \rangle$ is a Boolean function with input string $s = (x_1, \dots, x_L, t_1, \dots, t_L)$. Let $\Omega = \{s \in \Sigma^{(n+m)L} : F(s) = 1\}$, then

$$\text{Tr}(G^L) = \frac{1}{2^{mL}} |\Omega|.$$

Given a positive instance of the problem, it is therefore sufficient for Merlin to provide an efficiently verifiable witness for $|\Omega| \geq 2^{mL} \mu_+^L$. For a given s , inclusion in Ω can be efficiently checked. This can be seen by the fact that $\langle x | G(t) | y \rangle$ can be represented as a polynomial-time circuit and furthermore, the matrix elements $\langle x | G | y \rangle$ can be computed in polynomial-time, since the Hamiltonian is k -local. At this point a known **AM** protocol for approximate counting by Goldwasser and Sipser [15] is invoked. In this protocol Arthur sends a compressed string $y \in \{0, 1\}^b$ to Merlin, where $y = h(x)$. Here $h(x)$ is a universal Hash function and $x \in \{0, 1\}^k$ is the uncompressed string representing s . Arthur chooses the Hash function parameters so that $h(\Omega)$ is dense enough for him to be able to evaluate the volume of $h(\Omega)$ using the Monte Carlo method and thereby $|\Omega|$. Here the Monte Carlo method refers to producing a large number of compressed strings y ; evaluating the fraction of those for which $y \in h(\Omega)$, gives an estimate of the volume of $h(\Omega)$. However, it is not possible for Arthur to verify the inclusion of a compressed string $y \in h(\Omega)$, due to the nature of the Hash functions. At this point Merlin can provide a witness by sending the pre-images, x , of the compressed strings y . As we mentioned earlier, Arthur can efficiently check inclusion of x in Ω due to the Hamiltonian being local. It can be shown that Merlin only succeeds in sending a correct pre-image if $|\Omega| \geq 2^{mL} \mu_+^L$, which completes the proof.

We can observe that the same proof carries over to globally-stoquastic Hamiltonians as matrix elements of the global operator G , rather than local operators, are being used to evaluate the trace. Crucially $0 \leq \langle x | G | y \rangle \leq 1 \forall x, y \in \{0, 1\}^n$ for H a globally-stoquastic Hamiltonian. Furthermore, the fact that one can evaluate the matrix elements of G and therefore check whether a given string s is in Ω , hinges on G being local which is also the case for globally-stoquastic Hamiltonians.

In [8] it was shown that the **Local-Stoq-LH** is a complete problem for the class **StoqMA**. It was shown that for such Hamiltonians one can express, by an appropriate choice of parameters ϵ, β

$$\epsilon H + \beta I = \sum_j p_j U_j H_j U_j^\dagger,$$

where p_j is a properly normalised probability distribution and every H_j is a symmetric Z -matrix. For this to hold we require $H = \sum_s H_s$ where H_s is acting on a subset of at most k qubits and is a symmetric Z -matrix (see proof of Lemma 2 in the paper). As it stands, we can therefore not straightforwardly carry the proof over to globally-stoquastic Hamiltonians. Of course this does not mean necessarily that the k -local globally-stoquastic Hamiltonian problem \notin **StoqMA**, but it is an open question at this point to provide such a proof.

In addition to the general **Local-Stoq-LH**, the situation has also been analysed for some special cases of **Local-Stoq-LH**. Let us first consider the problem under the further constraint that the Hamiltonian admits a *guiding state*, as was done by Bravyi [7].

Definition 28 ([7] Definition 1). *Let H be a locally-stoquastic Hamiltonian. We will say that H admits a guiding state ϕ , iff there exists a pair of normalised n -qubit states ψ, ϕ with non-negative amplitudes in the standard basis, such that ψ is a ground state of H , the function $x \rightarrow \langle x|\phi\rangle$ is computable by a classical circuit of $\text{poly}(n)$ size and*

$$\langle x|\phi\rangle \geq \frac{\langle x|\psi\rangle}{\text{poly}(n)}$$

for all $x \in \{0, 1\}^n$

Definition 29 (Guided, locally-stoquastic local Hamiltonian problem). *A special case of Local-Stoq-LH where, in addition to the Hamiltonian being locally-stoquastic, it is promised that either $\lambda \leq \lambda_{\text{yes}}$ and H admits a guiding state or $\lambda \geq \lambda_{\text{no}}$*

Theorem 5. *Guided Local-Stoq-LH \in MA [7].*

We will first sketch out the proof as presented in [7]. In this paper Bravyi showed that there exists a probabilistic algorithm which runs in $\text{poly}(n)$ and a classical witness, such that for YES instances, the acceptance probability is close to 1 while for NO instances, the acceptance probability is close to 0.

The witness provided by Merlin in the case of a YES instance is a triple consisting of a real number λ_M which is the ground energy of H , a classical circuit computing the function $\phi_M(x) : \{0, 1\}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ corresponding to the amplitudes of some guiding state and a string $x_M \in \{0, 1\}^n$.

The classical, probabilistic algorithm Arthur uses in order to verify the witness is a random walk defined by the sequence of states $\gamma_0, \gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_L$ where for all i , $\gamma_i(x) \in \mathbb{Z}^{\geq} \forall x \in \{0, 1\}^n$ with

$$\gamma_0(x) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } x = x_M \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

In a similar fashion to the proof of Theorem 4, we introduce the matrix G

$$G = I - \frac{1}{2C}(H - \lambda_M I), \quad C = \sum_i \|H_i\|$$

Since H is a local, stoquastic Hamiltonian, it follows that G is non-negative and one can evaluate $\langle x|G|y\rangle$ in polynomial-time. The transition probability from the t^{th} state to the $(t+1)^{\text{th}}$ is then defined through

$$\gamma_{t+1}(y) = \sum_{x \in \{0, 1\}^n} \text{Pois}[\gamma_t(x) \frac{\phi(y)}{\phi(x)} \langle x|G|y\rangle],$$

where $\text{Pois}[\dots]$ is the Poisson distribution and $\phi(x)$ is a function which can be computed by a polynomial sized classical circuit, by adapting the circuit for $\phi_M(x)$, given the witness. As such the fraction $\phi(y)/\phi(x)$ can be efficiently evaluated. Furthermore, since $\text{Pois}[0] = 0$,

we get $\gamma_{t+1}(y) = 0$ with probability 1 when $\langle x | G | y \rangle = 0$. Therefore, at any time step there is only a polynomial number of states to transition to, since the number of points y for which $\gamma_{t+1}(y) \neq 0$ is at most $\text{poly}(n)$. This is clear as G is a local Hamiltonian, and so for every x there are at most $\text{poly}(n)$ bitstrings y such that $\langle x | G | y \rangle \neq 0$. Let's finally define the *total population size* at step t as

$$\Gamma_t = \sum_{x \in \{0,1\}^n} \gamma_t(x).$$

Upon receiving λ_M, ϕ_M, x_M Arthur makes L steps according to the random walk where at each step he checks if $\Gamma_t \leq \Gamma_{\max}$ (where Γ_{\max} is a predefined $\text{poly}(n)$ cutoff population size). If this criterion is not met he rejects the witness. If Arthur has not rejected the witness at time step t , the total population size is at most $\text{poly}(n)$ and he continues the walk. If he has not rejected the witness after L steps, he checks if $\Gamma_L \geq 1$ accepting the witness if the condition is satisfied, rejecting otherwise. For the proofs of completeness and soundness, we refer to the paper [7].

We can see that the argument put forward, equally applies to globally-stoquastic Hamiltonians. As in the proof of Theorem 4, we use the non-negativity and sparsity of the global operator G , which allows us to construct the random walk. This property holds both for locally and globally stoquastic Hamiltonians, since in both cases, the Hamiltonian is local operator and therefore its matrix elements can be efficiently computed.

In contrast, the argument used to show that the stoquastic, frustration-free local Hamiltonian problem is in **MA** as put forward by Bravyi and Terhal [10], is based on the non-negativity of the ground state presented in section 2.1.1 and a random walk over the n -bit strings for which the transition probability is dependent on the local projectors, Π_a , of the Hamiltonian

$$P_{x \rightarrow y} = \frac{\langle y | \psi \rangle}{\langle x | \psi \rangle} \langle x | G | y \rangle = \sqrt{\frac{\langle y | \Pi_a | y \rangle}{\langle x | \Pi_a | x \rangle}} \langle x | G | y \rangle \quad (3.1)$$

It is thus essential to this construction that the local projectors are non-negative, which is only ensured if the Hamiltonian is locally-stoquastic. As such, the proof is only applicable to locally-stoquastic Hamiltonians.

3.3.2 Sign problem free local Hamiltonian problem

In addition to the result that $\text{Global/Local-Stoq-LH} \in \mathbf{AM}$, it is interesting to see that for local Hamiltonians which don't suffer from the sign problem, the local Hamiltonian problem is in **AM** even if there does not exist a known, efficiently computable transformation which would make the Hamiltonian globally or locally-stoquastic. To make this more precise let us define *sign problem free* Hamiltonians as follows.

Definition 30 (Sign problem free Hamiltonian). *A Hamiltonian H on n qubits is sign problem free if, $\forall\beta, \forall N$*

$$\prod_{i=1}^N \langle x_i | (I - \beta H/N) | x_{i+1} \rangle \delta_{x_1, x_{N+1}} \geq 0 \quad \forall x_i \in \{0, 1\}^n$$

Lemma 5.1. *If H is a sign problem free Hamiltonian*

$$\tilde{Z}(\beta) = Z'(\beta) \quad \forall \beta$$

where $Z = \text{Tr}(e^{-\beta H})$, $\tilde{Z} = \text{Tr}(e^{-\beta \tilde{H}})$, and \tilde{H} is the stoquastified counterpart of H , see Definition 5.

Proof. Trotterizing and expanding $e^{-\beta(H)}$ as before, we obtain the following relation for the partition function:

$$\begin{aligned} Z'(\beta) &= \text{Tr}[e^{-\beta H}] = \text{Tr}[(e^{-\beta H/N})^N] = \text{Tr}\left[\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} (I - \beta H/N)^N\right] \\ &= \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{\{x\}} \prod_{i=1}^N \langle x_i | (I - \beta H/N) | x_{i+1} \rangle \delta_{x_1, x_{N+1}} \end{aligned}$$

We can convince ourselves that

$$\langle x | (I - \beta \tilde{H}/N) | y \rangle = |\langle x | (I - \beta H/N) | y \rangle| \quad \forall x, y \in \{0, 1\}^n \quad (3.2)$$

since for $x \neq y$,

$$|\langle x | (I - \beta H/N) | y \rangle| = |-\frac{\beta}{N} \langle x | H | y \rangle| = \langle x | -\beta \tilde{H}/N | y \rangle = \langle x | (I - \beta \tilde{H}/N) | y \rangle.$$

Shifting a Hamiltonian by some constant C does not affect its thermodynamic properties and only scales its partition function by a constant $e^{-\beta C}$. We can therefore take H to be such that $\langle x | H | x \rangle \leq 0$. Thus we get,

$$|\langle x | (I - \beta H/N) | x \rangle| = 1 + \frac{\beta}{N} |\langle x | H | x \rangle| = 1 - \frac{\beta}{N} \langle x | \tilde{H} | x \rangle = \langle x | (I - \beta \tilde{H}/N) | x \rangle$$

Furthermore, it follows from the definition of sign problem free Hamiltonian that

$$\prod_{i=1}^N \langle x_i | (I - \beta H/N) | x_{i+1} \rangle \delta_{x_1, x_{N+1}} = \prod_{i=1}^N |\langle x_i | (I - \beta H/N) | x_{i+1} \rangle| \delta_{x_1, x_{N+1}} \quad (3.3)$$

Combining Equations 3.2 and 3.3, we end up with

$$Z(\beta) = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{\{x\}} \prod_{i=1}^N \langle x_i | (I - \beta \tilde{H}/N) | x_{i+1} \rangle \delta_{x_1, x_{N+1}} = \tilde{Z}(\beta)$$

□

Proposition 9. *The local Hamiltonian problem for sign problem free Hamiltonians is in AM.*

Proof. We begin by noting that since

$$\langle H \rangle_Z = \frac{\text{Tr} H e^{-\beta H}}{Z} = -\frac{\partial}{\partial \beta} \ln(\text{Tr} e^{-\beta H}) = \frac{-\partial \ln Z(\beta)}{\partial \beta} \implies \langle H \rangle_Z = \langle \tilde{H} \rangle_{\tilde{Z}} \quad \forall \beta,$$

the ground energy of H and \tilde{H} are the same ($\langle H \rangle_{Z(\infty)} = \langle \tilde{H} \rangle_{\tilde{Z}(\infty)}$). As we have shown in the proof of Theorem 4, if H is globally/locally-stoquastic, there exists a protocol by which Merlin, can prove to Arthur, that the largest eigenvalue $\mu(G) \geq \mu_+$ for $G = 1/2(I - H/C)$. Define $\tilde{G} = 1/2(I - \tilde{H}/C)$. Recall that the smallest eigenvalue of H is the largest eigenvalues of G , and equally the smallest eigenvalue of \tilde{H} is the largest eigenvalue of \tilde{G} . Since the ground energy of H and \tilde{H} are the same, it follows that $\mu(G) = \mu(\tilde{G})$. Hence if $\mu(G) \geq \mu_+$, Merlin can provide a witness for $\mu(\tilde{G}) \geq \mu_+$. Since \tilde{H} is globally-stoquastic this completes the proof. \square

3.4 Summary

In this chapter we have motivated the use of the complexity theory formalism to classify physically relevant problems according to the amount of resources required to solve them. We presented some of the relevant classes and some of the known relations between them. Introducing the idea of Karp reductions we saw that there exist *complete* problems for certain classes, such as 3-SAT for **NP** and LocalHamiltonian for **QMA**. Finally, we looked at LocalHamiltonian in light of both locally and globally-stoquastic Hamiltonians as well as general sign problem free Hamiltonians. In the final chapter we will turn our focus towards the question of deciding whether a given Hamiltonian is stoquastic or not, again using complexity theory arguments.

Chapter 4

Complexity of deciding stoquasticity

In chapter two we have seen that a sufficient condition to avoid the sign problem in Monte Carlo simulations is for the Hamiltonian under consideration to be stoquastic. Clearly, from a practical point of view, it is crucial to be able to decide, whether a given Hamiltonian is stoquastic or not. As we have seen, there are two distinct notions of stoquasticity, therefore we will also consider two distinct problems associated with deciding each of them. Since stoquasticity is defined with respect to the matrix elements of a Hamiltonian and as such it is a basis dependent property, there is no reason to favour the standard basis over any other. If we are able to find a basis in which the Hamiltonian is stoquastic, we can circumvent the sign problem and, modulo convergence issues discussed, use the Monte Carlo method to estimate expectation values of observables. Since Hamiltonians are Hermitian matrices, they are diagonalisable, hence there always exists a basis in which they are globally/locally-stoquastic. Clearly finding a diagonalising basis is an impractical approach as the complexity for diagonalising such matrices scales exponentially with number of qubits in the system [40]. Furthermore, being able to diagonalise the Hamiltonian and identifying the smallest diagonal element, involves solving **NP**-complete and **QMA**-complete problems such as the ones seen in the previous chapter. As we said earlier, we don't expect to be able to do this in general with the use of polynomial size quantum/classical circuits.

4.1 Deciding stoquasticity in a fixed basis

Let us start by addressing the problem of deciding whether a given Hamiltonian is stoquastic in the computational basis.

Definition 31. *Given some real, k -local Hamiltonian H on n qubits, define **GlobalStoq** [26] as the problem of deciding whether*

$$\langle x | H | y \rangle \leq 0 \quad \forall x \neq y \in \{0, 1\}^n$$

Definition 32. *Given some real, k -local Hamiltonian on n qubits, define **LocalStoq** as the problem of deciding whether there exists a k -local decomposition $H = \sum_i H_i$ where each H_i*

acts non-trivially on a subset of at most k qubits, such that for all i

$$\langle x | H_i | y \rangle \leq 0 \quad \forall x \neq y \in \{0, 1\}^n$$

In chapter two we have studied the necessary condition for a k -local globally-stoquastic Hamiltonian to admit a k' -local, locally-stoquastic decomposition. Therefore **LocalStoq** is a special case of that problem where we fix $k' = k$. We consider the grouping of the Pauli terms in H into terms $H(x)$. Here each term in $H(x)$ flips the same qubits, labeled by $x \in \{0, 1\}^n$. Furthermore, grouping of the terms according to the subset of k qubits they act non-trivially on, labelled by $\mathbf{i} = (i_1, \dots, i_k)$, we get the decomposition

$$H = \sum_x H(x) = \sum_{\mathbf{i}} \sum_x H_{\mathbf{i}}(x).$$

For H to be locally-stoquastic, there has to exist at least one decomposition, such that all terms $H_{\mathbf{i}} = \sum_x H_{\mathbf{i}}(x)$ are symmetric Z -matrices. Thus, this corresponds to checking the existence of a decomposition for which conditions (2.3), (2.4) are satisfied for all \mathbf{i} . Since these conditions consist of a set of linear equalities and inequalities, we conclude that **LocalStoq** is a feasibility problem which we can, in principle, solve using linear programming techniques. We need to check how the run-time of such a linear program will scale with system size and locality of the decomposition.

We have one linear inequality for each value of x . Let $0 < l \leq k$ be the Hamming weight of x , we can check that there are at most $\binom{k}{l}$ such inequalities for each k -tuple and at most $\binom{n}{k}$ different k -tuples \mathbf{i} , due to the Hamiltonian being k -local. In the worst case we therefore have a total of $\binom{k}{l} \binom{n}{k}$ conditions and thus $\mu \binom{k}{l} \binom{n}{k}$ number of variables where μ is a multiplicity factor related to the number of terms in $\tilde{H}_{\mathbf{i}}(x)$. For $k - l$ an even number, μ can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha = & \sum_{p=0}^{p=k-l} \left[\prod_p (k-l-p) + \sum_{n=2p+2}^{m=k-l} \left(\sum_{m=n}^{m=k-l} \prod_m (k-l-m) \right) \right. \\ & \left. + \sum_{n=2p+3}^{m=k-l-1} \left(\sum_{m=n}^{m=k-l-1} \prod_m (k-l-m) \right) \right] = \text{poly}(k-l). \end{aligned}$$

Linear programming has worst case runtime polynomial in the number of variables [14], [22]. Hence the worst case runtime for finding a decomposition for which the Hamiltonian is locally stoquastic, or deciding that such a decomposition does not exist, is $\mathcal{O}(\text{poly}(k-l) \binom{k}{l} \binom{n}{k})$.

So we see that the complexity of deciding local stoquasticity will depend on the locality of the decomposition considered. As long as we consider a $(k < \mathcal{O}(\log n))$ -local decomposition, there exists a $\text{poly}(n)$ algorithm which finds a feasible solution, if one exists. In contrast, the problem of deciding whether k -local Hamiltonian is globally-stoquastic, as discussed in chapter 2, requires one to decide whether for all x

$$\alpha(x) \leq \min_{u,v} [\langle u | -\tilde{H}(x) | v \rangle],$$

where $\alpha(x), \tilde{H}(x)$ are defined according to equation 2.2. It is clear that evaluating the right hand side is not always trivial and in fact we will show that it entails **NP**-complete problems.

Theorem 6. *GlobalStoqu is **coNP**-complete*

Proof. It is straightforward to see that **GlobalStoq** is in **coNP**, as there exists an efficiently verifiable witness for its **NO** instances in the form of bitstrings $x, y \in \{0, 1\}^n$ for which $\langle x | H | y \rangle > 0$. Since H is a local Hamiltonian, we can efficiently evaluate such matrix elements and thus verify the witness.

We proceed by showing that **GlobalStoq** is **coNP**-hard and hence **coNP**-complete by reducing **PS** (Theorem 2) to it. Given an instance of **PS** with graph $G = (V, E)$ such that $|V| = n$, define the $n + 1$ qubit Hamiltonian

$$H = (K + \epsilon^+)X_{n+1} - \sum_{(i,j) \in E} Z_i Z_j X_{n+1} - \sum_{i \in V} Z_i X_{n+1},$$

where $0 < \epsilon^+ < 1$. As we can factor X_{n+1} from every term in H , $\langle x | H | y \rangle \neq 0$ only when bitstrings x, y differ in the $(n + 1)^{th}$ bit. Let us denote the first n bits of x, y as x' and the $(n + 1)^{th}$ as x_{n+1}, y_{n+1} respectively. We have

$$\langle x | H | y \rangle = \langle x' | (K + \epsilon^+) - \sum_{(i,j) \in E} Z_i Z_j - \sum_{i \in V} Z_i | x' \rangle \langle x_{n+1} | X_{n+1} | y_{n+1} \rangle.$$

For a **NO** instance of **GlobalStoq** there exist $x = x'x_{n+1}$ and $y = x'\bar{x}_{n+1}$

$$\langle x | H | y \rangle = (K + \epsilon^+) - \sum_{(i,j) \in E} S_i S_j - \sum_{i \in V} S_i > 0$$

$$\sum_{(i,j) \in E} S_i S_j + \sum_{i \in V} S_i < (K + \epsilon^+),$$

where $S_i = \langle x' | Z_i | x' \rangle \in \{+1, -1\}$, $i \in \{0, 1\}$. Since the left hand side is an integer and $\epsilon^+ < 1$,

$$\exists \{S_i\} : \sum_{(i,j) \in E} S_i S_j + \sum_{i \in V} S_i \leq K.$$

Therefore, **NO** instances of **GlobalStoq** correspond to **YES** instances of **PS**. Similarly for a **YES** instance of **GlobalStoq** we have that $\forall x \neq y \langle x | H | y \rangle \leq 0$. Again using the fact that $0 < \epsilon^+ < 1$, we have

$$\forall \{S_i\} : \sum_{(i,j) \in E} S_i S_j + \sum_{i \in V} S_i > K$$

and thus, **YES** instances of **GlobalStoq** correspond to **NO** instances of **PS** which completes the reduction. \square

In chapter two we saw that $H = X_1 \otimes (E_0 - H_{\text{Ising}})$ is not locally-stoquastic when a three-local decomposition is considered. In some cases it was shown that a locally-stoquastic decomposition can be found when we consider four-local decompositions.

Proposition 10. *The class of Hamiltonians $H = X_1 \otimes (E_0 - H_{\text{Ising}})$ with E_0 the ground energy of H_{Ising} is, in general, k -locally-stoquastic only when a $k > \mathcal{O}(\log(n))$ decomposition is considered for $H_{\text{Ising}} = \sum_{(i,j) \in E} J_{ij} Z_i Z_j$ on $G = (V, E)$.*

The proof is by contradiction. Assume Proposition 10 does not hold and recall that every locally-stoquastic Hamiltonian is trivially globally-stoquastic. Using Theorem 6 in conjunction with the fact that **LocalStoq** is a problem in **P** (given that the locality considered is $k < \mathcal{O}(\log(n))$) and the assumption that **coNP**-complete problems do not admit polynomial time algorithms, we get a contradiction. If all $H = X_1 \otimes (E_0 - H_{\text{Ising}})$ are ($k < \mathcal{O}(\log(n))$)-locally-stoquastic we can efficiently decide **GlobalStoq** by deciding **LocalStoq**.

4.2 Deciding stoquasticity under basis transformations

Allowing basis transformations under which the Hamiltonian becomes stoquastic can be seen as a systematic way to cure the sign problem and was first studied by Klassen and Terhal [27] and Marvian et al [33]. What one is looking for are efficiently implementable basis transformations under which the Hamiltonian becomes stoquastic, thereby extending the class of stoquastic Hamiltonians. We are therefore looking at a certain subgroup $U_s \subset U(2^n)$ such that the circuit implementing elements of U_s can be simulated in $\text{poly}(n)$ time on a classical computer.

Definition 33 (Effectively stoquastic Hamiltonian). *The Hamiltonian H is effectively stoquastic if there exists a unitary U such that*

$$UHU^\dagger = H',$$

where H' is a real, symmetric Hamiltonian with $\langle x | H' | y \rangle \leq 0$ for all $x \neq y \in \{0, 1\}^n$ and the number of Pauli terms in H' is $\text{poly}(n)$ and can be efficiently determined.

Note that, in addition to being efficient to implement, it is important for the transformation U to not lead to an exponential number of Pauli terms in H' , as this would render calculations of matrix elements impractical. We will consider two major classes of such transformations, namely local unitaries and Clifford circuits. We will show that for two-local Hamiltonians with one-local terms, the problem of deciding whether it is effectively stoquastic under local unitaries is a **NP**-complete problem, while there exists an efficient algorithm which decides this in the absence of one-local terms [26],[27]. By considering Clifford circuits we can expand the class of effectively stoquastic 1-D Hamiltonians even further.

4.2.1 Local unitary rotations

We will refer to unitary transformations $U \subset U(2^n)$ under which a Hamiltonian is effectively stoquastic as *sign-curing transformations*. Accordingly, we define the problem

Definition 34 ($\text{LocalSignCure}(H)$). *Given a Hamiltonian, H on n qubits, $\text{LocalSignCure}(H)$ is the problem of determining whether there exists a set of single qubit unitary transformations $U_a \in SU(2)$ such that $UHU^\dagger = H'$ where $U = \bigotimes_{a=1}^n U_a$ and H' is a symmetric Z -matrix.*

In [33] the authors showed that it is possible to reduce 3-SAT to $\text{LocalSignCure}(H)$ for H a three-local Hamiltonians with one-local terms, when restricting the local unitaries to be $\bigotimes_{a=1}^n U_a$ for $U_a \in \{W, I\}$. Here W is the single qubit Hadamard matrix. In [26] we extended this result by showing that it holds true even for a certain class of two-local Hamiltonians without further restrictions on $U_a \in SU(2)$.

Theorem 7. *There exists a class of two-local Hamiltonians, H_{SAT} , on n qubits for which $\text{LocalSignCure}(H_{SAT})$ is **NP**-complete.*

Theorem 7 was proven in [26], here we present an alternative but very similar proof by Klassen, Marvian, Ioannou and Terhal. Before turning to the proof of the theorem itself, let us review some useful concepts for the analysis of two-local Hamiltonians introduced by Klassen and Terhal [27].

Definition 35 (β matrix, S, P [27]). *Given a two qubit Hamiltonian $H = \sum_{i,j \in \{I,X,Y,Z\}} \alpha_{ij} \sigma_i \otimes \sigma_j$ where $\sigma_x = X, \sigma_y = Y, \sigma_z = Z, \sigma_I = I$. We define the β matrix and vectors S, P of H as*

$$\beta = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_{XX} & \alpha_{XY} & \alpha_{XZ} \\ \alpha_{YX} & \alpha_{YY} & \alpha_{YZ} \\ \alpha_{ZX} & \alpha_{ZY} & \alpha_{ZZ} \end{bmatrix}, \quad S = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_{XI} \\ \alpha_{YI} \\ \alpha_{ZI} \end{bmatrix}, \quad P = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_{IX} \\ \alpha_{IY} \\ \alpha_{IZ} \end{bmatrix}$$

Expressing the interactions between pairs of qubits in terms of β matrices allows us to map the local unitary transformations on H to orthogonal rotations on the β matrices.

Proposition 11. *There exists a correspondence between the pair of single qubit unitary transformations U_1, U_2 acting on a two qubit Hamiltonian $H \rightarrow (U_1 \otimes U_2)H(U_1 \otimes U_2)^\dagger$ and the pair of $SO(3)$ rotations O_1, O_2 acting on the β matrix $\beta \rightarrow O_1 \beta O_2^\dagger$ [27].*

The proof is an extension of the well known correspondence between $SO(3)$ and $SU(2)$, commonly used to describe single qubit unitaries in terms of the Bloch sphere.

Proposition 12. *A two qubit Hamiltonian $H = \sum_{i,j \in \{I,X,Y,Z\}} \alpha_{ij} \sigma_i \otimes \sigma_j$ is stoquastic iff $\alpha_{IY} = \alpha_{YI} = \alpha_{XY} = \alpha_{YX} = \alpha_{ZY} = \alpha_{YZ} = 0$ and $\alpha_{XX} \leq -|\alpha_{YY}|, \alpha_{IX} \leq \alpha_{ZX}, \alpha_{XI} \leq \alpha_{ZX}$ [27]*

The proof follows directly from Definition 6. To prove Theorem 7 we make use of a novel gadget, in the form of interactions with ancilla qubits, which restricts any sign-curing transformations to a discrete subset of the local unitary transformations (namely tensor products of single qubit Hadamard and identity operators). Being able to restrict the continuous set of possible $SU(2)$ transformations to a discrete one, means that there exists an efficiently verifiable witness for YES instances of the problem, which places **LocalSignCure** in **NP**. We then proceed by showing that we can map any 3-SAT to a Hamiltonian in such a way that there is a correspondence between YES instances of 3-SAT and YES instances of **LocalSignCure**. Clearly, this encoding serves as a polynomial time reduction and by virtue of the fact that 3-SAT is **NP**-hard, we can conclude that **LocalSignCure** is **NP**-complete.

As we have discussed, an instance of 3-SAT is given by a set of m clauses C_i , $i = 1, \dots, m$. Define a triplet of qubits (u_i, v_i, w_i) for each clause, corresponding to the variables x_u, x_v, x_w respectively. We now construct the Hamiltonian

$$H_{\text{SAT}} = H_{\text{clause}} + H_{\text{tie}} + H_{\text{triangle}},$$

where H_{clause} represents the clauses $C_i \forall i \geq 1$ in terms of interactions between qubits u_i, v_i, w_i . The assignment of values 1 or 0 to x_u will correspond to applying local Hadamard or identity transformations to the corresponding qubit. As variables x_u can be occurring in multiple clauses, we must enforce the same local unitary on all qubits $u_i \forall i$, corresponding to the same variable x_u . To this end we introduce one mediator qubit u_0 for each variable in the 3-SAT instance. We then couple u_0 with all qubits $u_i \forall i$ through the interactions of H_{tie} . Finally, for every qubit u_i for $i \geq 1$ we introduce a pair of ancilla qubits u'_i, u''_i which are connected with each other as well as with u_i through the interaction H_{triangle} . This is done so as to fix the possible sign-curing local unitaries to the subset $\{I, X, W, XW\}$. More concretely we have

$$H_{\text{clause}} = \sum_{i=1}^m H_{u_i, v_i, w_i}^{111}$$

where,

$$\begin{aligned} H_{abc}^{111} = & -2(X_a + X_b + X_c) - (Z_a + Z_b + Z_c) \\ & - (X_a Z_b + X_a Z_c + X_b Z_c + X_c Z_b + X_c Z_a + X_b Z_a). \end{aligned}$$

Next we define the tying Hamiltonian

$$H_{\text{tie}} = \sum_{u=1}^n \sum_{i: x_u^\alpha \in C_i} G_{u_0, u_i}^\alpha$$

where $\alpha \in \{0, 1\}$ and we have used the notation $x_u^0 \in C_i$ when x_u appears in that clause and $x_u^1 \in C_i$ when \bar{x}_u is used instead. Here $G_{a,b}^\alpha$ is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} G_{a,b}^0 &= -2X_a X_b - Z_a Z_b \\ G_{a,b}^1 &= W_b G_{a,b}^0 W_b, \end{aligned}$$

where W_b denotes the Hadamard gate on qubit b . Finally, the interactions of the triangle gadget are given by

$$H_{\text{triangle}} = \sum_{u=1}^n \sum_{\alpha} \sum_{i: x_u^\alpha \in C_i} T_{u_i},$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} T_a = & - (X_a X_{a'} + Z_a Z_{a'} + X_a X_{a''} + Z_a Z_{a''}) \\ & - \frac{1}{2} (X_{a'} X_{a''} - Y_{a'} Y_{a''}) - Z_{a'} Z_{a''}. \end{aligned}$$

We now want to show that by the use of the triangle gadget, it is sufficient to consider unitaries consisting of tensor products of local Hadamard and identity operators.

Lemma 7.1. *If $\langle x | U^\dagger H_{\text{SAT}} U | y \rangle \leq 0 \forall x \neq y \in \{0, 1\}^n$ for some $U = \bigotimes_{a=1}^N U_a$ where U_a are single-qubit unitaries, there also exists $C = \bigotimes_{a=1}^N C_a$ with $C_a \in \{I, W\}$ such that $\langle x | C^\dagger H_{\text{SAT}} C | y \rangle \leq 0 \forall x \neq y \in \{0, 1\}^n$ [26]*

Proof. Note first that there are no one-local terms involving ancilla qubits a'_i, a''_i in H_{triangle} and that $\beta_{a', a''}$ is diagonal, full rank and non-degenerate. Using the correspondence for β matrices discussed earlier, we can see that the only sign-curing transformations correspond to signed permutations on $\beta_{a', a''}$ which correspond to single qubit Clifford transformations. On the other hand we note that there exist one local terms of the form

$$\mu X_a + \nu Z_a$$

with $\mu, \nu \leq -1$ on every clause qubit coming from H_{clause} .

In order for the unitary transformations on the qubits a, a', a'' to keep the Hamiltonian real, the transformation on a has to be restricted so that the corresponding orthogonal transformation on $\beta_{aa'}, \beta_{aa''}$ matrix is in the XZ plane. Thereby one avoids creating one local terms proportional to Y_a . This in turn restricts the unitaries on a' and a'' to induce orthogonal transformations in the XZ plane, so as to avoid creating $X_a Y'_a$ type terms. The explicit form of such $SO(3)$ rotations is given by

$$O_a = R_\gamma(\theta_a) = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta_a) & 0 & \sin(\theta_a) \\ 0 & \gamma & 0 \\ -\gamma \sin(\theta_a) & 0 & \gamma \cos(\theta_a) \end{bmatrix}$$

with $\gamma = \pm 1$. The rotations $O_{a'}$ and $O_{a''}$ are also required to be of this form with the further restriction of being signed permutations which leads to $\theta_{a'/a''} = 0, \pi$ and $\gamma = \pm 1$ or $\theta_{a'/a''} = \pi/2, 3\pi/2$. From the definition of H_{triangle} we can see that $\beta_{a, a'}$ is the identity in the XZ sub-block. The condition of diagonality of $O_a^T \beta_{a, a'} O_a$ means that when $\theta_{a'} = 0 \bmod \pi$ we require $\theta_a = 0 \bmod \pi$ and respectively when $\theta_{a'} = \pi/2 \bmod \pi$ we require $\theta_a = \pi/2 \bmod \pi$. Using the further restriction on O_a , imposed by the fact that the sign-curing transformation

should keep the coefficient of X_a non-positive, we are left with the following orthogonal rotations in the XZ plane and the corresponding unitary transformations

$$\begin{aligned} A &= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow I, & B &= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow X \\ C &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow W, & D &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow XW \end{aligned}$$

Hence the only sign-curing transformations are equivalent to I, X, W, XW .

To complete the proof we need to show that for a given O_a , from the restricted set above, we can always find $O_{a'}, O_{a''}$ such that H_{triangle} is stoquastic. Indeed, such a choice is given by

$$O_a = O_{a'} = O_{a''}$$

Since H_{triangle} is stoquastic in the computational basis, choosing all rotations being identity is clearly sufficient. We can convince ourselves that any choice of $O_a = A, B, C$ or D leads to diagonal $\tilde{\beta}_{aa'}, \tilde{\beta}_{aa''}$ satisfying the conditions in Proposition 12.

Having established that the transformations on qubits u_i for $i \geq 1$ needs to be taken from $\{I, X, W, XW\}$ we now need to show that the same holds also for the mediator qubits u_0 . Note again that there are one-local terms on qubits u_i for $i \geq 1$ coming from H_{clause} but none such terms for u_0 . When u_i is connected to u_0 through G^0 , we can see that applying I or X to u_i restricts us to transforming u_0 using I or X as well, in order for the conditions in Proposition 12 to be satisfied. Similarly when we apply W or XW to u_i we have to apply W or XW . When u_i and u_0 are connected via G^1 this correspondence is swapped i.e applying I or X on u_i means we need to apply W or XW on u_0 and applying W or XW to u_i requires us to apply I or X on u_0 for conditions in Proposition 12 to be satisfied.

We finally note that if there exists a sign-curing transformation with local operators taken from $\{I, X, W, XW\}$, there also exists a sign-curing transformation with operators taken from $\{I, W\}$ since the additional transformation by X occurring in $\{X, XW\}$ does not affect the conditions for stoquasticity as was shown in [33]. \square

Corollary 7.1. $\text{LocalSignCure}(H_{\text{SAT}})$ is contained in **NP**

To complete the proof of Theorem 7, we need to show the reduction from 3-SAT

Proposition 13. A 3-SAT instance given by m clauses C_i on n variables is satisfiable if and only if there exists $C = \bigotimes_{a=1}^N C_a$ with $N = 9m + n$ and $C_a \in \{I, W\}$ such that $\langle x | C^\dagger H_{\text{SAT}} C | y \rangle \leq 0 \forall x \neq y \in \{0, 1\}^n$. Therefore $3\text{-SAT} \leq_K \text{LocalSignCure}(H_{\text{SAT}})$

Proof. Let's define a satisfying assignment to the 3-SAT instance as $x_{\text{SAT}} = (x_1, \dots, x_n)$ with $x_i \in \{1, 0\}$. We have to construct a map between x_{SAT} and $C = \bigotimes_{i=1}^N W^{\alpha_i}$ with $\alpha_i \in \{1, 0\} \forall i$. Indeed, such a map exists and can be summarised as follows.

1. For all u apply W on qubit u_0 if $x_u = 0$ and I if $x_u = 1$

2. For every u and all qubits u_i with $i \geq 1$ apply
- (a) W if $x_u = 0$ and I if $x_u = 1$ when C_i uses x_u .
 - (b) I if $x_u = 0$ and W if $x_u = 1$ when C_i uses \bar{x}_u .

To check the correctness of the encoding, let us focus on its effect on H_{tie} . We can convince ourselves that

$$W_a^\alpha \otimes W_b^\beta G_{ab}^0 W_a^\alpha \otimes W_b^\beta$$

is stoquastic only for the choice of the pair $(\alpha, \beta) = (0, 0)$ or $(\alpha, \beta) = (1, 1)$. Since $G_{ab}^1 = W_b G_{ab}^0 W_b$ it follows that the only choice of pairs for which G_{ab}^1 is a symmetric Z-matrix is $(\alpha, \beta) = (0, 1)$ or $(\alpha, \beta) = (1, 0)$. Recalling that G_{ab}^0 is used when u_0 is linked to a qubit corresponding to x_u and G_{ab}^1 when linked to one corresponding to \bar{x}_u , we see that the proposed choice of Hadamard/identity transformations turns H_{tie} into a symmetric Z-matrix. Now consider the effect on H_{clause} by first noting that H_{abc}^{111} is stoquastic. In fact, one can easily verify that

$$W_a^\alpha \otimes W_b^\beta \otimes W_c^\gamma H_{abc}^{111} W_a^\alpha \otimes W_b^\beta \otimes W_c^\gamma$$

is stoquastic for all choices of (α, β, γ) except $(1, 1, 1)$ (corresponding to an unsatisfied clause). As we discussed above, the choice of transformations on u'_i, u''_i is the same as the one for u_i . Hence we see that indeed a satisfying assignment for the 3-SAT instance can be translated directly to a choice of local unitary rotations C_a , such that the Hamiltonian is stoquastic under $C = \bigotimes_{a=1}^N C_a$.

To complete the other direction of the proof we need to show that any sign-curing transformation involving local unitaries taken from $\{I, W\}$ ensures, via the proposed mapping, that the assignment of variables is satisfying the 3-SAT instance. As we have seen, it is not possible to achieve sign-curing of H via distributing the one local terms in H_{clause} to H_{tie} . Thus, we can treat every term in H_{clause} on its own, demanding a sign-curing transformation to consists of local unitaries C_a such that every term H_{u_i, v_i, w_i}^{111} is cured independently. Furthermore, H_{tie} effectively couples all qubits in H_{clause} corresponding to the same Boolean variable, hence the unitary on each qubit u_i for $i \geq 1$ represents the assignment of x_u . Thus, an assignment is satisfying only if the corresponding unitary is sign-curing. \square

Corollary 7.2. $3\text{-SAT} \leq_K \text{LocalSignCure}(H_{\text{SAT}}) \implies \text{LocalSignCure}(H_{\text{SAT}})$ is *NP-hard*

Combining the fact that $\text{LocalSignCure}(H_{\text{SAT}})$ is in **NP** and also **NP-hard**, we conclude that it is **NP-complete**. However, as was shown [26],[27] there exists a $\text{poly}(n)$ algorithm for $\text{LocalSignCure}(H_{2\text{-loc}})$ when $H_{2\text{-loc}}$ is a strictly two-local Hamiltonian. In other words we see that the absence of one-local terms in the Hamiltonian leads to a reduction in the complexity of the problem. In the same spirit the authors in [17] examined the possibility of easing rather than curing the sign problem. From our analysis of the relative error of the expectation value of some observable, we have seen that we need to maximise the average sign in order to minimise the relative error. Indeed, if we can find transformations under

which $\langle \text{sgn}Q(\mathbf{x}) \rangle_{\tilde{H}} = 1$ we can avoid the sign problem altogether. As it stands, this is intractable, as it involves non-convex optimization over a non-linear function. However, the authors propose an easily computable measure for non-stoquasticity, which in some cases also serves as a good measure for the sign problem. They furthermore proceed to show that even easing the sign problem, by minimising this measure when allowing local orthogonal rotations, is in fact a **NP**-complete problem.

4.2.2 Going beyond local unitaries

As we have seen, deciding whether there are sign-curing transformations for strictly two-local Hamiltonians can be efficiently done when we restrict to local unitaries. Studying the proposed algorithm [27] we can construct relatively simple three qubit Hamiltonians on a line, which cannot be sign cured using local unitaries only. As there is a folklore belief that 1-D Hamiltonian do not suffer from the sign problem, we would like to examine whether the effectively stoquastic class of 1-D Hamiltonians can be extended by considering different basis transformations. Going beyond local unitaries, the natural class of transformations to consider are general Clifford circuits. It is a known fact that such circuits are classically simulatable and therefore fit exactly into the criteria we laid out earlier. Furthermore, it has been shown in [11], that the world-line Monte Carlo method described in chapter one, converges in quasi-polynomial time (in system size) for the class of 1-D stoquastic Hamiltonians when $\beta = \mathcal{O}(\log n)$. Unfortunately, this is not quite strong enough a result due to the restriction on β . We will, nevertheless, briefly look at the proof as it provides an example of how convergence of MCMC is studied.

Convergence analysis for 1-D stoquastic Hamiltonians

Before going over the method of sign-curing 1-D Hamiltonians using Clifford circuits, let us briefly discuss the argument set out by Crosson and Harrow [11] showing convergence of the Monte Carlo in quasi-polynomial time for 1-D stoquastic Hamiltonians. To illustrate the ideas going into proving convergence, we will go over the proof for the 1-D generalized transverse Ising models with long-range interactions. We will also see how single site updates can lead to a non-ergodic chain, as well as a way to treat this pathology.

The Hamiltonian under consideration is given by

$$H = - \sum_{j=1}^n \Phi_j X_j + \sum_{j=1}^n K_j^z Z_j + \sum_{j,k=1}^n K_{jk}^{zz} Z_j Z_k$$

with $K_j^z \in [-1, 1]$ and $|K_{jk}^{zz}| \leq |i - j|^{-(2+\xi)}$ for $\xi > 0$.

In order to quantify how far from the stationary distribution we are at time t , we introduce the variational distance [32]

$$d_{\mathbf{x}}(t) := \max_{S \subseteq \Omega} |P^t(\mathbf{x}, S) - \pi(S)| = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\mathbf{y} \in \Omega} |P^t(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) - \pi(\mathbf{y})|,$$

where $P^t(\mathbf{x}, \cdot)$ is the distribution of the chain at time t , when \mathbf{x} is the starting state. The time needed to equilibration, given by t_{equil} , is such that, given some bound ϵ we have $d_{\mathbf{x}}(t_{\text{equil}}) \leq \epsilon$. For the worst-case starting state we have an equilibration time

$$\tau(\epsilon) = \tau(\epsilon) = \max_{\mathbf{x} \in \Omega} \min_t [t : d_{\mathbf{x}}(t) \leq \epsilon \forall t \geq t'].$$

We then define the mixing time $\tau_{\text{mix}} := \tau(1/4)$, noting that $\tau(\epsilon) = \tau_{\text{mix}} \log \epsilon^{-1}$. The rate of convergence to the stationary distribution can then be quantified through the study of "canonical paths" [32],[30].

Definition 36 ([32]). *A canonical path from state $\mathbf{x} \rightarrow \mathbf{y}$ is defined as the sequence of states $\gamma_{xy} = (\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_k)$, such that $\sigma_{i+1} \in \Omega$ can be reached by $\sigma_i \in \Omega$ with the transition rule defined for the chain, for all $i \in \{1, \dots, k-1\}$ and $\sigma_1 = \mathbf{x}, \sigma_k = \mathbf{y}$. Denote the set of all canonical paths by Γ .*

Definition 37 ([11]). *The congestion of the chain, with respect to the set Γ is defined by*

$$R(\Gamma) := \max_{t=(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v})} \left\{ \frac{\sum_{\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}: t \in \gamma_{xy}} \pi(\mathbf{x})\pi(\mathbf{y})k}{\pi(\mathbf{u})P(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v})} \right\}$$

where t runs over all possible pairs (\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}) , such that \mathbf{u} can be reached from \mathbf{v} with the transition rule of the chain.

It can then be shown (see e.g [32]) that small congestion implies short mixing time. In fact the two are linearly related via

$$\tau_{\text{mix}} \leq R \ln(1/\min_{\mathbf{x}}[\pi(\mathbf{x})]) + 2R \ln 4.$$

For the pair of states $e = (\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v})$, let $\Gamma(e)$ be the set of canonical paths in Γ which contain this edge. The congestion can be evaluated using a so called encoding which is a function $\eta_e : \Gamma(e) \rightarrow \Omega \times \Theta$, such that at most $|\Theta|$ paths containing edge (\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}) are mapped to the same state in Ω , for all pairs (\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) . Assuming that there exists some A such that

$$\pi(\mathbf{x})\pi(\mathbf{y}) \leq A\pi(\mathbf{u})\pi(\eta_e(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y})) \quad \forall \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y} \in \Omega \quad (4.1)$$

It can then be shown that the congestion is bounded by

$$R \leq \frac{A|\Theta|}{\min_{(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}')} P(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}')} \quad (4.2)$$

We therefore need to evaluate or at least find a bound for the right hand side of Equation 4.2 After performing the Suzuki-Trotter decomposition [44] and the "quantum to classical" mapping described earlier, we end up with a configuration space $\Omega \in \{0, 1\}^{n \times L}$ where L is the *poly*(n) number of time slices. We represent a configuration as $\mathbf{x} = (x_{1,1}, \dots, x_{n,L}) = (\tilde{x}_1, \dots, \tilde{x}_L)$ where $x_{i,j} \in \{0, 1\}$ and $\tilde{x}_i \in \{0, 1\}^n$. Similar to the example of the classical Ising

Hamiltonian discussed in chapter one, we use a uniform proposal distribution, flipping a random bit $x_{i,j}$. The acceptance probability of such a move can then be expressed as [11]:

$$P(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') := \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2nL} \min\{1, \pi(\mathbf{x}')/\pi(\mathbf{x})\}, & \mathbf{x} \neq \mathbf{x}' \\ 1 - \sum_{\mathbf{x}'' \neq \mathbf{z}} P(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}''), & \mathbf{x} = \mathbf{x}' \end{cases}$$

Note that when the Hamiltonian of the system is a general 1-D, locally stoquastic Hamiltonian, it turns out that the numerator of $\pi(\mathbf{x}')/\pi(\mathbf{x})$ can be zero when using single site updates. This corresponds to a zero probability of accessing configuration \mathbf{x}' and therefore leads to a non-ergodic chain. In order to make the chain ergodic we can add weak, off diagonal terms to the Hamiltonian. In order to find a bound on the congestion, we can lower bound the minimum transition probability by evaluating a bound on $\pi(\mathbf{x}')/\pi(\mathbf{x})$. For the details of this calculation we refer to the original paper.

We can now describe how we construct canonical paths using single site updates given two spin configurations $\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y} \in \Omega$ with

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{x} &= (x_{1,1}, \dots, x_{L,1}, x_{1,2}, \dots, x_{1,n}, \dots, x_{L,n}) \\ \mathbf{y} &= (y_{1,1}, \dots, y_{L,1}, y_{1,2}, \dots, y_{1,n}, \dots, y_{L,n}) \end{aligned}$$

The canonical path $\gamma_{\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}}$ is constructed through a $(n \times L)$ step process in which we replace each bit in \mathbf{x} with the corresponding one in \mathbf{y} , one world line at a time (i.e updating bits $x_{i,j}$ in an order of increasing j before updating $x_{i+1,j}$ in the same order). That means we start from the first qubit and move along the time axis (Trotter steps) updating the configuration in each step. Repeating for the second qubit etc. until we have updated the bit $x_{L,n} \rightarrow y_{L,n}$. For every pair of bits $x_{r,m} \neq y_{r,m}$ we add an edge (\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}) where

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{u} &= (y_{1,1}, \dots, y_{r-1,m}, x_{r,m}, x_{r+1,m}, \dots, x_{L,n}) \\ \mathbf{v} &= (y_{1,1}, \dots, y_{r-1,m}, y_{r,m}, x_{r+1,m}, \dots, x_{L,n}). \end{aligned}$$

In other words the states in the sequence $\gamma_{\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}} = (\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_k)$ are such that σ_i and σ_{i+1} differ at exactly one bit corresponding to an earlier world line and/or Trotter step. The number of edges in the canonical path $\gamma_{\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}}$ is therefore given by the number of bits differing in \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}

In order to find the value of A needed to satisfy Equation 4.1, we need to compute

$$\frac{\pi(\mathbf{x})\pi(\mathbf{y})}{\pi(\mathbf{u})\pi(\eta)} = e^{-\beta(E(\mathbf{x})+E(\mathbf{y})-E(\mathbf{u})-E(\mathbf{x}))} \quad (4.3)$$

where $E : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is the classical energy function introduced through the Suzuki-Trotter "quantum to classical" mapping. Using a certain decoding $\eta_{\mathbf{u} \rightarrow \mathbf{v}}$, see [11], we can evaluate Equation 4.3 and thus a lower bound for A , satisfying Equation 4.1. Using this we can show that the congestion, Equation 4.2, is polynomially bounded in the system size [11].

Clifford Circuits for Sign-curing

We will now study under what circumstances general Clifford circuits can be used for the purpose of sign-curing 1-D qubit Hamiltonians. Clifford circuits only contain gates

belonging to the Clifford group; the subgroup of the unitary group which takes Paulis to Paulis. More precisely [38]:

Definition 38 (Pauli group P_n). *The Pauli group P_n is composed of the n -fold tensor products of $P_i \in \{I, X, Y, Z\}$ with overall phase ± 1 or $\pm i$. The group multiplication rule is the usual matrix multiplication.*

Definition 39 (Clifford group C_n). *The Clifford group on n qubits is the normalizer of P_n in the unitary group $U(2^n)$*

$$C_n = \{U \in U(2^n) | U P U^\dagger \in P_n \ \forall P \in P_n\}$$

Perhaps the most important result concerning Clifford circuits, is the so called Gottesman-Knill theorem, stating that circuits which are build entirely using Hadamard, C-NOT and phase gates, can be simulated in polynomial time on a classical computer [1]. Since these three gates are generators of the Clifford group [38], it follows that any Clifford circuit can be simulated in polynomial time.

For our purpose it is not necessary to specify the Clifford circuit itself, but only its action on the Paulis. In general it is enough to define the transformation for a generating set of P_n i.e define how X_i, Z_i are transformed $\forall i$, to fully specify how all $P \in P_n$ are transformed [38]. Crucially one can show that given a partially defined Clifford channel, it is always possible to complete the channel [16]. Given $\{P_i\}$ and $\{P'_i\}$ with the same (anti-)commutation and product relations, there exists a Clifford $C : P_i \rightarrow P'_i$. Thus, given $H = \sum_i \alpha_i P_i$ for $\alpha_i \in \mathbb{R}$, it is sufficient to find a new set of Pauli operators, satisfying the same (anti)-commutation relations as those in H , while preserving the product relations between them. Since this is the only restriction for the transformation to be a valid Clifford, it is clear that the locality of the Paulis need not be preserved. However, the action of Cliffords on Paulis is, by definition, a bijective map. Hence, although the locality of the transformed Hamiltonian might increase, the number of Pauli terms in its decomposition is unchanged.

Recalling the proof of Theorem 4 we can show that the k -local Hamiltonian problem for H is in **AM**, when H can be sign-cured by Clifford circuits. Since H is k -local, $H = \sum_i \alpha_i P_i$ will contain $poly(n)$ terms P_i and therefore we can evaluate $\langle x | G | y \rangle$ in $poly(n)$ time. Since the number of Pauli terms in the decomposition of H' is still $poly(n)$, we can efficiently evaluate $\langle x | G' | y \rangle$, even though H' might be k' -local with $k' > k$. Given a proof in the form of a string $s \in \Sigma^{m \times n}$ from Merlin, Arthur can efficiently verify when $s \in \Omega$. The remainder of the proof carries through identically as before.

In the next section we will examine two families of Hamiltonians which are effectively stoquastic under Clifford transformations while being non-stoquastic under local unitaries. As we will see, the locality of the transformed Hamiltonian is increased from two to four in the worst case. Therefore, the proof of containment of the stoquastic, frustration free local Hamiltonian problem in **MA** still carries through as it is still possible to simulate the random walk defined by equation 3.1, in $poly(n)$ time.

Consider the Heisenberg XYZ model on a 1-D chain with arbitrary coupling coefficients

$$H = \sum_i \alpha_i^{XX} X_i X_{i+1} + \alpha_i^{YY} Y_i Y_{i+1} + \alpha_i^{ZZ} Z_i Z_{i+1}$$

Using the representation in terms of β matrices, introduced earlier, the above Hamiltonian is represented by $\beta_{i \ i+1} = \text{diag}(\alpha_i^{XX}, \alpha_i^{YY}, \alpha_i^{ZZ}) \forall i$. As has been shown in [27], H can be sign-cured if there exist signed permutation matrices Π_i , with unit determinant (corresponding to single-qubit Cliffords) such that

$$\Pi_i \beta_{i \ i+1} \Pi_{i+1} = \tilde{\beta}_{i \ i+1},$$

where $\tilde{\beta}_{i \ i+1} = \text{diag}(\tilde{\alpha}_i^{XX}, \tilde{\alpha}_i^{YY}, \tilde{\alpha}_i^{ZZ})$ and $\tilde{\alpha}_i^{XX} \leq -|\tilde{\alpha}_i^{YY}|$ for all i . When $\beta_{i \ i+1}$ and $\beta_{i+1 \ i+2}$ are both of rank larger than 2, we require $\Pi_i = \Pi_{i+1} = \Pi_{i+2}$, for $\beta_{i \ i+1}$ and $\beta_{i+1 \ i+2}$ to both be diagonal. This condition allows us to construct examples of Hamiltonians which cannot be sign-cured using local unitaries.

Consider the following three qubit, XYZ Hamiltonian on a line

$$H_{123} = 2X_1X_2 + Z_1Z_2 + X_2X_3 + 3Y_2Y_3 + 2Z_2Z_3,$$

which corresponds to $\beta_{12} = \text{diag}(2, 0, 1)$, $\beta_{23} = \text{diag}(1, 3, 2)$. We see that the YY coefficient is the largest in absolute value of the coefficients in β_{23} and in particular $|\alpha_{23}^{YY}| > |\alpha_{23}^{XX}|$. We can convince ourselves that there does not exist a signed permutation under which $\tilde{\alpha}_{23}^{XX} \leq -|\tilde{\alpha}_{23}^{YY}|$, $\tilde{\alpha}_{12}^{XX} \leq -|\tilde{\alpha}_{12}^{YY}|$. Indeed, the same argument holds for every Hamiltonian which contains $\beta_{ij} = \text{diag}(a, 0, b)$ with $a > b$ and $\beta_{jk} = \text{diag}(c, d, e)$ with $c < e < d$ and $a, b, c, d, e \neq 0$. Having established that local unitaries are not always sufficient to sign-cure 1-D XYZ Hamiltonians, we will show that there exist Clifford transformations which do this for a large subclass of the 1-D XYZ model.

Proposition 14. *XYZ Heisenberg Hamiltonians in 1-D are effectively stoquastic under general Clifford transformations if, represented as a series of $\beta_{i \ i+1}$ matrices, at least every second $\beta_{i \ i+1}$ satisfies $\det(\beta_{i \ i+1}) \geq 0$.*

Proof. Start by noting that all Paulis acting non-trivially on the same pair of qubits mutually commute

$$\left[X_i X_j, Y_i Y_j \right] = \left[X_i X_j, Z_i Z_j \right] = \left[Y_i Y_j, Z_i Z_j \right] = 0$$

while Paulis acting non trivially on one common qubit satisfy the (anti-)commutation relations defined by

$$\begin{aligned} \left\{ X_i X_j, Y_i Y_k \right\} &= \left\{ X_i X_j, Z_i Z_k \right\} = \left\{ Y_i Y_j, Z_i Z_k \right\} = 0, \\ \left[X_i X_j, X_i X_k \right] &= \left[Y_i Y_j, Y_i Y_k \right] = \left[Z_i Z_j, Z_i Z_k \right] = 0, \end{aligned}$$

For the 1-D XYZ model, these conditions can be summarised in terms of the (anti-)commutation graph in figure 4.1.

Figure 4.1: Top: Graph summarising the (anti-)commutation relations between the Pauli terms in the XYZ Heisenberg model. An edge between two vertices representing Paulis indicates anticommutation between them while absence of an edge indicates that they commute. Bottom: Representation of Hamiltonian transformed under Clifford, preserving the structure $\Delta_{(i,j)} = \pm 1$.

Any one-to-one map from the Paulis in the Hamiltonian to any other set of Paulis, corresponds to a Clifford if the commutation and anticommutation relations as well as the product relations are preserved. Hence, there exist Clifford transformations summarised in figure 4.1, such that $C : H \rightarrow H'$

$$\begin{aligned}
H &= \sum_i \alpha_{ii+1}^{XX} X_i X_{i+1} + \alpha_{ii+1}^{YY} Y_i Y_{i+1} + \alpha_{ii+1}^{ZZ} Z_i Z_{i+1} \\
&= \sum_{i=2m+1 \forall m \in \mathbb{Z}} \alpha_{ii+1}^{XX} X_i X_{i+1} + \alpha_{ii+1}^{YY} Y_i Y_{i+1} + \alpha_{ii+1}^{ZZ} Z_i Z_{i+1} \\
&+ \sum_{i=2m \forall m \in \mathbb{Z}} \alpha_{ii+1}^{XX} X_i X_{i+1} + \alpha_{ii+1}^{YY} Y_i Y_{i+1} + \alpha_{ii+1}^{ZZ} Z_i Z_{i+1} \\
H' &= \sum_{i=2m+1 \forall m \in \mathbb{Z}} \Delta_i^Z \alpha_{ii+1}^{XX} Z_i + \Delta_{i+1}^Z \alpha_{ii+1}^{YY} Z_{i+1} - \Delta_i^Z \Delta_{i+1}^Z \alpha_{ii+1}^{ZZ} Z_i Z_{i+1} \\
&+ \sum_{i=2m \forall m \in \mathbb{Z}} (\Delta_{(i-1,i+1)}^{XX} \alpha_{ii+1}^{XX} X_{i-1} X_{i+1} + \Delta_{(i,i+2)}^{XX} \alpha_{ii+1}^{YY} X_i X_{i+2} \\
&- \Delta_{(i-1,i+1)}^{XX} \Delta_{(i,i+2)}^{XX} \alpha_{ii+1}^{ZZ} X_{i-1} X_i X_{i+1} X_{i+2}),
\end{aligned}$$

with sign assignments $\Delta_i^{\sigma_u}, \Delta_{(i,j)}^{\sigma_u \sigma_v} \in \{+1, -1\}$. We need to check for which coefficients $\alpha_{ii+1}^{XX}/\alpha_{ii+1}^{YY}/\alpha_{ii+1}^{ZZ}$ we can find sign assignments such that all coefficients of XX and $XXXX$ type terms in H' are negative and hence the Hamiltonian is stoquastic. The possible four cases are listed below.

1. $\det(\beta_{i \ i+1}) > 0$

(a) $\alpha_{ii+1}^{XX}, \alpha_{ii+1}^{YY}, \alpha_{ii+1}^{ZZ} > 0$

(b) $\alpha_{ii+1}^{XX}, \alpha_{ii+1}^{YY} < 0, \alpha_{ii+1}^{ZZ} > 0$ or any permutation thereof.

2. $\det(\beta_{i \ i+1}) < 0$

(a) $\alpha_{ii+1}^{XX}, \alpha_{ii+1}^{YY}, \alpha_{ii+1}^{ZZ} < 0$

(b) $\alpha_{ii+1}^{XX}, \alpha_{ii+1}^{YY} > 0, \alpha_{ii+1}^{ZZ} < 0$ or any permutation thereof.

3. $\det(\beta_{i \ i+1}) = 0$

(a) $\alpha_{ii+1}^{XX} > 0, \alpha_{ii+1}^{ZZ} < 0, \alpha_{ii+1}^{YY} = 0$ or any permutation thereof.

(b) $\alpha_{ii+1}^{XX}, \alpha_{ii+1}^{ZZ} > 0, \alpha_{ii+1}^{YY} = 0$ or any permutation thereof.

(c) $\alpha_{ii+1}^{XX}, \alpha_{ii+1}^{ZZ} < 0, \alpha_{ii+1}^{YY} = 0$ or any permutation thereof.

We can convince ourselves that H' is stoquastic in cases 1(a), 1(b) as well as 3(a)-(c).

1. (a) Choose $\Delta_{(i-1,i+1)}^{XX} = \Delta_{(i,i+2)}^{XX} = -1$.

- (b) Choose $\Delta_{(i,i+2)}^{XX} = \Delta_{(i-1,i+1)}^{XX} = +1$ if $\alpha_{ii+1}^{XX}, \alpha_{ii+1}^{YY} < 0$.
 Choose $\Delta_{(i,i+2)}^{XX} = -1, \Delta_{(i-1,i+1)}^{XX} = +1$ if $\alpha_{ii+1}^{XX} > 0$.
 Choose $\Delta_{(i-1,i+1)}^{XX} = -1, \Delta_{(i,i+2)}^{XX} = +1$ if $\alpha_{ii+1}^{YY} > 0$.
2. (a) There does not exist a suitable sign assignment such that the transformed Hamiltonian is a symmetric Z-matrix, as the product relation $(X_i X_j)(Y_i Y_j) = -Z_i Z_j$ needs to be preserved.
- (b) As we can map from an interaction of this type, via a Clifford transformation to an interaction of the type 2(a) the same argument holds for the inexistence of a suitable sign assignment.
3. (a) Choose $\Delta_{(i,i+2)}^{XX} = -1, \Delta_{(i-1,i+1)}^{XX} = +1$ if $\alpha_{ii+1}^{XX} > 0$.
 Choose $\Delta_{(i-1,i+1)}^{XX} = -1, \Delta_{(i,i+2)}^{XX} = +1$ if $\alpha_{ii+1}^{YY} > 0$.
 Choose $\Delta_{(i,i+2)}^{XX} = -1, \Delta_{(i-1,i+1)}^{XX} = +1$ if $\alpha_{ii+1}^{ZZ} > 0, \alpha_{ii+1}^{XX} = 0$.
 Choose $\Delta_{(i-1,i+1)}^{XX} = -1, \Delta_{(i,i+2)}^{XX} = +1$ if $\alpha_{ii+1}^{ZZ} > 0, \alpha_{ii+1}^{YY} = 0$.
- (b) Choose $\Delta_{(i-1,i+1)}^{XX} = \Delta_{(i,i+2)}^{XX} = -1$.
- (c) Choose $\Delta_{(i-1,i+1)}^{XX} = \Delta_{(i,i+2)}^{XX} = +1$ if $\alpha_{ii+1}^{ZZ} = 0$.
 Choose $\Delta_{(i-1,i+1)}^{XX} = +1, \Delta_{(i-1,i+1)}^{XX} = -1$ if $\alpha_{ii+1}^{YY} = 0$.
 Choose $\Delta_{(i-1,i+1)}^{XX} = -1, \Delta_{(i-1,i+1)}^{XX} = +1$ if $\alpha_{ii+1}^{XX} = 0$.

□

We have seen that the 1-D XYZ Heisenberg model is effectively stoquastic under the application of general Clifford transformations unless there are two-qubit interactions $\alpha_{ii+1}^{XX} X_i X_{i+1} + \alpha_{ii+1}^{YY} Y_i Y_{i+1} + \alpha_{ii+1}^{ZZ} Z_i Z_{i+1}$ such that $\det(\beta_{ii+1}) < 0$.

We now want to generalise this result to Hamiltonians on a line represented by general quasi-monomial β matrices. A quasi-monomial β matrix [26] is one with at most one non-zero entry for every row and column.

Proposition 15. *1-D Hamiltonians representable by a series of quasi monomial matrices $\beta_{i \ i+1}$ are effectively stoquastic under general Clifford transformations if $\det(\beta_{i \ i+1}) \geq 0$ for $i = 2k$ or $i = 2k + 1$ with $k \in \mathbb{N}$ (i.e every second β in the series has non-negative determinant).*

Proof. We can group the terms of the Hamiltonian into those acting on the even pairs of qubits $H_{\text{even}} = \sum_{i=2k} H_{ii+1}$ and those acting on the odd pairs $H_{\text{odd}} = \sum_{i=2k+1} H_{ii+1}$ (here $k \in \mathbb{N}$). We can find signed permutations Π_i, Π_{i+1} with determinant 1 for all $\beta_{i \ i+1}$ with $i = 2k$, such that $\Pi_i \beta_{i \ i+1} \Pi_{i+1}^\dagger = \tilde{\beta}_{i \ i+1}$ with diagonal $\tilde{\beta}_{i \ i+1}$ [26]. At the same time all $\beta_{i \ i+1}$ with $i = 2k + 1$, remain in quasi-monomial form under such signed permutations (albeit the entries might be shuffled). This can be seen by the fact that conjugating a quasi-monomial matrix with signed permutation matrices will always give a quasi-monomial matrix. As mentioned before, signed permutations with unit determinant correspond to local Clifford

transformations [27]. Note that the Pauli operators represented by a quasi-monomial β matrix mutually commute (this was shown explicitly in the case where β is diagonal). Furthermore, note that the (anti-)commutation relations between the Paulis in any quasi-monomial $\beta_{i-1\ i}$, $\beta_{i\ i+1}$ and $\beta_{i+1\ i+2}$, have the same structure independently of the exact form of the quasi-monomial β matrices. Indeed, the (anti-)commutation relations will have the same form as the one illustrated in figure 4.1 where $\beta_{i-1\ i}$, $\beta_{i\ i+1}$ and $\beta_{i+1\ i+2}$ are diagonal.

After having diagonalised every $\beta_{i\ i+1}$ matrix, for even i , using local Clifford transformations, we can perform a further Clifford transformation in order to sign-cure the Hamiltonian. We can map the three Paulis corresponding to non-zero coefficients of $\beta_{i\ i+1}$, for odd i , to $Z_i, Z_{i+1}, \pm Z_i Z_{i+1}$ choosing the signs as to preserve the product relations. As these operators are diagonal in the computational basis, their signs are irrelevant with regards to stoquasticity. At the same time we map all Paulis in the diagonal β matrices ($\beta_{i\ i+1}$ for even i) to $\Delta_{(i,i+2)}^{XX} X_i X_{i+2}$, $\Delta_{(i-1,i+1)}^{XX} X_{i-1} X_{i+1}$ and $-\Delta_{(i-1,i+1)}^{XX} \Delta_{(i,i+2)}^{XX} X_{i-1} X_i X_{i+1} X_{i+2}$. The ability to find sign assignments such that the coefficients of those Paulis are all negative will depend on the sign of the determinant (as for the XYZ Heisenberg Hamiltonians). We therefore see that a Hamiltonian on a line represented by quasi-monomial β matrices is effectively stoquastic if there exist signed permutations $\{\Pi_i\}$ under which every other β matrix is of the form $\beta_{ii+1} = \text{diag}[\alpha_{ii+1}^{XX}, \alpha_{ii+1}^{YY}, \alpha_{ii+1}^{ZZ}]$ and $\det[\beta_{ii+1}] \geq 0$ for all i . Since the determinant of β_{ii+1} is unchanged under local Cliffords, this means that every Hamiltonian on a line represented by quasi-monomial β matrices is effectively stoquastic if every second β matrix has determinant ≥ 0 . □

Both in the case of 1-D Hamiltonians represented by quasi-monomial matrices as well as the special case of the 1-D XYZ Heisenberg model, we have seen that the only obstacle to prove that such Hamiltonians are always effectively stoquastic arose when the determinant of some β was negative. One could overcome this problem by allowing signed permutations with determinant -1 on the β matrices. Such transformations correspond to reflections in \mathbb{R}^3 and therefore to $O(3)$ transformations rather than $SO(3)$ transformations. If we can show that such transformations correspond to a valid encoding according to Definition 1 in [12], we can show that 1-D Hamiltonians representable by a series of quasi-monomial matrices are effectively stoquastic.

Finally, we will go over an example of a three qubit Hamiltonian on a triangular graph that cannot be sign-cured using local unitaries. The reason this Hamiltonian is of interest is that it is the only known example to which the resummation technique introduced by Hen [18],[19] has been applied. We will see that this type of Hamiltonian can be sign-cured when Clifford circuits are considered.

$$H = \alpha_{ZZ}(Z_1 Z_2 + Z_2 Z_3 + Z_1 Z_3) + \alpha_{XX}(X_1 X_2 + X_2 X_3 + X_1 X_3)$$

with $\alpha_{XX}, \alpha_{ZZ} > 0$. Again employing β matrices to represent H we have

$$\beta_{12} = \beta_{13} = \beta_{23} = \text{diag}(\alpha_{XX}, 0, \alpha_{ZZ})$$

and due to the triangular configuration, we see that there does not exist any signed permutation $\Pi_i \beta_{ij} \Pi_j^T = \tilde{\beta}_{ij}$ such that all $\tilde{\beta}_{ij}$ correspond to a stoquastic Hamiltonian. As in the 1-D chain, the Paulis acting non-trivially on the same pair of qubits mutually commute. One can find an assignment of Paulis which are either tensor products of X and I , tensor products of Y and I or tensor products of Z and I such that the (anti-)commutation and product relations are preserved. For the resulting Hamiltonian to be stoquastic we also need to ensure that for every YY term there exists a XX term, acting non-trivially on the same qubits, such that $\alpha_{XX} \leq -|\alpha_{YY}|$. For the given Hamiltonian we choose the following transformation

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_{ZZ} Z_1 Z_2 + \alpha_{XX} X_1 X_2 &\rightarrow -\alpha_{ZZ} X_1 X_2 - \alpha_{XX} X_2 X_3 \\ \alpha_{ZZ} Z_1 Z_3 + \alpha_{XX} X_1 X_3 &\rightarrow \alpha_{ZZ} Z_1 Z_2 + \alpha_{XX} Z_2 Z_3 \\ \alpha_{ZZ} Z_2 Z_3 + \alpha_{XX} X_2 X_3 &\rightarrow \alpha_{XX} Y_1 Y_2 + \alpha_{ZZ} Y_2 Y_3 \end{aligned}$$

We can see that these are proper Clifford transformations as they preserve the (anti-)commutation relations, depicted in figure 4.2, as well as the product relations since $(Z_1 Z_2)(Z_2 Z_3) = Z_1 Z_3 \rightarrow (-X_1 X_2)(Y_1 Y_2) = Z_1 Z_2$ and $(X_1 X_2)(X_2 X_3) = X_1 X_3 \rightarrow (-X_2 X_3)(Y_2 Y_3) = Z_2 Z_3$. We can confirm that the resulting Hamiltonian is indeed stoquastic as $\tilde{\alpha}_{XX}^{12} \leq -|\tilde{\alpha}_{YY}^{12}|$, $\tilde{\alpha}_{XX}^{23} \leq -|\tilde{\alpha}_{YY}^{23}|$ and the interaction between qubits 1 and 2 is purely classical. Here $\tilde{\alpha}$ corresponds to the coefficients of the respective Paulis post Clifford transformation.

4.3 Summary

In this last chapter we have seen that even in a fixed basis, deciding whether a Hamiltonian is globally-stoquastic is a hard problem. On the other hand we can decide whether it is locally-stoquastic in polynomial time, using linear programming, as long as the locality of the decomposition is $k < \mathcal{O}(\log n)$. We then showed that allowing sign-curing, local unitary transformations can be an effective technique to avoid the sign problem if the Hamiltonian is strictly two-local. If there are one-local terms present, we showed that the problem is **NP**-complete. We then studied the convergence analysis for the world-line Monte Carlo method for the 1-D generalised transverse field Ising model. Finally, we considered Clifford circuits as a mean to sign-cure 1-D Hamiltonians, showing that a large class of these can efficiently be transformed into a stoquastic form.

Figure 4.2: Top: Graph summarising the (anti-)commutation relations of Pauli operators in $H = \alpha_{ZZ}(Z_1Z_2 + Z_2Z_3 + Z_1Z_3) + \alpha_{XX}(X_1X_2 + X_2X_3 + X_1X_3)$. Bottom (anti-)commutation graph of the transformed Pauli operators. We can see that the structure is preserved.

Chapter 5

Conclusions

5.1 Summary of results

In this thesis we have analysed local and global stoquasticity showing that the two notions are distinct. We showed that although local stoquasticity always implies global stoquasticity, the reverse statement only holds true for two-local Hamiltonians while it does not hold for $(k \geq 3)$ -local ones [26],[9]. Furthermore, we showed that the condition needed to be satisfied for a globally stoquastic Hamiltonian to admit a locally stoquastic decomposition is closely related to a generalised notion of frustration-free Hamiltonians. Building on this, we were able to show that deciding whether a Hamiltonian is globally stoquastic in a fixed basis, is a **coNP**-complete, while deciding if it is locally stoquastic is a problem in **P** (as long as the locality considered is $k < \mathcal{O}(\log(n))$). From our analysis of the Monte Carlo method we saw that the local Hamiltonian problem for *sign problem free* Hamiltonians is in **AM** [9] even if they are not stoquastic. Similarly we have shown that the local Hamiltonian problem for globally stoquastic Hamiltonians is also in **AM** and that the same problem is in **MA** when we further promise that it admits a guiding state. We then proceeded to show that the problem of deciding whether there exists a local unitary transformation which cures the sign problem for generic qubit Hamiltonians, is **NP**-complete for two-local Hamiltonians with one-local terms improving on the result of [33]. Finally, we showed that a large class of 1-D Hamiltonians is effectively stoquastic under the action of general Clifford circuits.

5.2 Outlook

There is a plethora of open questions to be answered. Firstly, it would be interesting to see if one can come up with a systematic way to find the locality k such that for all $k' < k$ a given globally stoquastic H is not locally stoquastic while for all $k' \geq k$ it is. Secondly, one could try to expand the class of effectively stoquastic Hamiltonians even further, for example by considering shallow depth quantum circuits building on the results presented here and [26]. Alternatively one could see if it is possible to engineer,

by the use of perturbation theory, stoquastic Hamiltonians which approximately simulate non-stoquastic Hamiltonians in their low energy subspace, building on [12]. This later point is of particular interest in the light of [37], where it is claimed that one can indeed achieve this in practice. As we have seen, the results concerning rigorously proven bounds on the run-time for Monte Carlo simulations are scarce. Therefore, being able to devise new techniques for such convergence analysis or, using existing ones to characterise new classes of Hamiltonians, would also be worthwhile. Finally, it would be interesting to obtain average-case complexity results for the stoquastic local Hamiltonian problem and variations thereof.

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Erklärung:

Hiermit erkläre ich, die vorliegende Arbeit selbständig verfasst zu haben und keine anderen als die in der Arbeit angegebenen Quellen und Hilfsmittel benutzt zu haben.

München, den 11/09/2019

Marios Ioannou